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1. Summary

This report constitutes Deliverable 2.2 on Transformative change pathways on trade, legal actions, and corporate governance, as part of TCforBE Work Package 2 which maps, characterises and assesses consumer country transformative governance innovations for biodiversity and equity. The report consists of three peer reviewed published articles (Santika, Nelson et al. 2024; Santika, Nelson et al., 2025, Banwell et al 2025).

These studies on transformative governance innovations reiterate that global demand for tropical cash crops—especially oil palm, cocoa, and coffee—is accelerating deforestation, with high-income countries driving the highest and fastest-growing consumption. Although governments are exploring measures such as supply-chain due diligence and environmental provisions in trade agreements, the studies evidence that market-based initiatives fall short of transformative change innovations that positively impact biodiversity and equity, due to the continued and expansionary logic of global markets. More transformative, post-growth approaches rooted in commoning and localised economic activity are proposed as pathways to reduce socio-ecological harm.

Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) could be a pathway as they increasingly include environmental clauses. However, a global analysis of 195 countries (1990–2018) shows that RTAs often worsen environmental impact shifting, with wealthy countries outsourcing resource-intensive production—energy, raw materials, water, and land—to poorer nations. Environmental provisions were assessed to have limited long-term effectiveness, instead reinforcing global inequalities. Stronger consumption-based governance, rigorous footprint accounting, and ecological premiums on resource-intensive imports are required for transformative change to take place.

Legal and societal pathways for transformative sustainability were identified, including mainstream tools such as supply-chain based voluntary measures such as certification and regulations. More radical approaches were identified, such as introducing legal rights of nature, ecocide law, and principles of restorative justice. The authors conclude that combining socio-legal strategies that challenge human–nature separation and capitalist growth imperatives is essential to achieve pluriversal, multi-species justice.

2. Introduction

This report constitutes Deliverable 2.2 on Transformative change pathways on trade, legal actions, and corporate governance, as part of TCforBE Work Package 2 which maps, characterises and assesses consumer country transformative governance innovations for biodiversity and equity. The report consists of three peer reviewed published articles:

Santika, T., Nelson, V., Flint, M., MacEwen, M., Cerretelli, S., & Brack, D. (2024). Leverage points for tackling unsustainable global value chains: market-based measures versus transformative alternatives. *Sustainability Science*, 19(1), 285-305. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01430-0>

Santika, T., Nelson, V., Hagggar, J., & Thushari, I. (2025). Trade agreements and environmental provisions: a counterfactual analysis of environmental impact shifting under global economic inequality. *Global Environmental Change*, 93, 103028. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2025.103028>

Banwell, S., Nelson, V., & Dehbi, F. (2025). Achieving sustainability transformations for multi-species justice: assessing the potential of diverse legal pathways and societal struggles. *Sustainability Science*, 20(3), 1017-1035. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-025-01627-5>

3. Paper 1: Leverage points for tackling unsustainable global Value Chains: market-based measures versus transformative alternatives

Santika, T., Nelson, V., Flint, M., MacEwen, M., Cerretelli, S., & Brack, D. (2024). Leverage points for tackling unsustainable global value chains: market-based measures versus transformative alternatives. *Sustainability Science*, 19(1), 285-305

Abstract Tropical forests are rapidly disappearing due to the expansion of cash crops to meet demands from distant markets. Pressing concerns on deforestation impacts resulting from the global trade of tropical commodities have led some high-income countries' governments to consider diverse regulatory and trade levers to tackle the problem. These include proposals for new supply chain due diligence legislation concerning imports of forest-risk products and the inclusion of environmental measures in trade deals. To contribute to this debate, we conducted a comprehensive analysis of existing data on global trade and consumption patterns of tropical commodities, attribution of commodity production to deforestation, trade agreements, and progress in the implementation of crop sustainability standards. We used global data on key tropical commodities of oil palm, cocoa, and coffee. Our study shows that high-income countries have the highest per capita consumption for the three commodities evaluated and that consumption rates have dramatically increased in the last two decades. We discuss a range of measures that can potentially be required to tackle deforestation in global supply chains, which are currently being considered by policymakers, before discussing the kinds of post-growth, convivial approaches that are often excluded by the framing. Given the inherent expansionary nature of global market dynamics, we show that market-based initiatives are inadequate to tackle continuing deforestation and socio-ecological degradation. More transformative solutions amplify commoning and post-growth approaches are required to lead to some uncoupling of trade and territorialising of economic activity to fit within planetary boundaries and allow for plural values.

Keywords Consumption · Planetary boundaries · Post-growth · Telecoupling · Trade policy · Tropical deforestation

2.1 Introduction

Tropical forests presently cover about 1.84 billion hectares and account for 45% of the tropical region (FAO 2020). These forests cover more land area than forests in other biomes (i.e. 11, 16, and 27% in subtropical, temperate, and boreal regions) (FAO 2020) and store the highest carbon density (Pan et al. 2013; Harris et al. 2021). They are vital in capturing carbon and serve as a natural buffer to climate change (Brinck et al. 2017; Mitchard 2018). They harbour high biological diversity and various endemic species and are important in maintaining ecosystem functions and services essential to support local livelihoods, food security, and human well-being in developing countries (Davis et al. 2020; Pillay et al. 2022). However, tropical forests have been subjected to rapid deforestation and forest degradation and escalated carbon emissions from land-use change in recent decades (Taubert et al. 2018; Brando et al. 2019; Hansen et al. 2020). About 60% of total forest losses were associated with the expansion of cropland, pasture, and industrial tree plantations (Pendrill et al. 2019). This expansion is driven by increased demand for tropical commodities such as oil palm, soybeans, cocoa, coffee, beef, and rubber from consumers in the international market (Hoang and Kanemoto 2021; Sun et al. 2022) and growing affluent populations in the commodities' producing countries (Munroe et al. 2019; Xiong et al. 2021).

High-income countries (HICs), including members of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), are recognised as among the leading international consumers of tropical deforestation embodied in trade (Pendrill et al. 2019). Between 2015 and 2017, the OECD HICs' imports of key forest-risk commodities were associated with an estimated total deforestation risk of 358,235 ha per year (equivalent to 3.08 ha per 10,000 people per year) (Pendrill et al. 2022). This is primarily due to limited production, overall high consumption rates per capita, and the presence of large food and feed industries in these countries (Bager and Lambin 2020; Fuchs et al. 2020). Besides OECD countries, Asian emerging economies such as China and India are also among the

leading consumers of forest-risk commodities over the same period, although their trade-associated deforestation risk is significantly lower compared to the OECD HICs (i.e. 166,850 and 46,302 ha per year, or equivalent to 1.15 and 0.33 ha per 10,000 people per year) (Pendrill et al. 2022). Estimation of the extent of deforestation associated with crop production has so far been carried out using rudimentary data on the country or sub-national-level crop production and forest cover change, raising uncertainties in their accuracy (Pendrill et al. 2019, 2022). Given the recent availability of spatiotemporally explicit data on the change in crop distribution in major producing countries, such as oil palm (Xu et al. 2020; Descals et al. 2021), soybeans (Song et al. 2021), and cocoa (Abu et al. 2021), there is room to evaluate more accurately the actual extent of deforestation attributed to the production of tropical crops.

Environmental provision has generally been lacking in trade policies (Brandi et al. 2020; Abman et al. 2021). The relationship between the environment and trade, and the legal and economic implications, have been much debated over the last thirty years, especially since the creation of the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 1995 (Brack 2013; Bigdeli 2014). The relatively small number of WTO disputes involving policies aimed overtly at protecting the environment have been scrutinised extensively without generating consensus on any way forward (Brack 2013; WTO 2022a). However, pressing concerns on deforestation risk embodied in tropical commodity imports, perpetuated by problems of global inequality (Sun et al. 2022), have recently led some HIC governments, including the EU and UK, to propose new legislation that mandates companies and businesses involved in forest-risk commodity imports to comply with the supply chain due diligence and reporting requirements (Environment Act 2021; European Commission 2021). These proposals marked the beginning of a formal legislative process aimed at reducing deforestation associated with trade (Brandi et al. 2020; Abman et al. 2021), although many details are yet to be addressed in the secondary regulations before they come into force by 2024.

One of the challenges in formulating secondary regulations in deforestation-free trade legislation is to devise an appropriate due diligence mechanism for each regulated crop without breaching the countries' commitment under existing international trade agreements. Sustainability standards are one of the relevant mechanisms that have long been discussed within the WTO. Sustainability standards seek to ensure that commodities are cultivated, sourced, and processed through a predefined set of sustainability threshold indicators, covering environmental and social dimensions. Private standards are not generally used in national-wide trade policy, i.e. in determining a country's levels of import or export duty, or regulatory requirements governing imports and exports. However, they have recently been used by the Switzerland authorities to verify compliance with the sustainability criteria included in the EFTA–Indonesia CEPA (European Free Trade Association–Indonesia Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement), thereby rendering compliant products eligible for reductions in import duty (Larrea et al. 2021; Limenta 2022).

Here, we assess the potential route toward a more environmentally responsible trade of tropical crops drawing from existing data on global trade and consumption patterns of tropical commodities, attribution of commodity production to deforestation, incorporation of environmental elements in trade agreements, and progress in the implementation of crop sustainability standards. More specifically, we seek to answer four related research questions: (1) What is the current global trade of tropical commodities, and what are the commodity consumption patterns across countries with different development statuses? (2) How is the production of tropical crops associated with deforestation and how does the estimation of crop-induced deforestation vary by approach? (3) How have environmental clauses been incorporated into trade agreements and how robust are they in reflecting environmental goals? (4) What is the evidence of sustainability standards' effectiveness and impact? By addressing these questions and carrying out a comprehensive analysis of relevant data, we discuss potential leverage points pertaining to global trade which can potentially be enhanced to reduce environmental damage to the biodiverse tropical landscape and what additional measures or more transformative approaches might be required to achieve environmental goals with respect to tackling deforestation in supply chains.

2.2 Materials and methods

We analysed data on three key forest-risk commodities: oil palm, cocoa, and coffee. These commodities were chosen to represent various geographical foci (with differing (large-scale

plantations and small- and medium-scale farms). Oil palm is produced largely in tropical Asia (Indonesia and Malaysia) (Descals et al. 2021), cocoa in tropical Africa (Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana) (Abu et al. 2021), and coffee in tropical Latin America (Brazil and Colombia) (OvalleRivera et al. 2015). Large-scale plantations are recognised as the primary actors in oil palm production and supply chain (Descals et al. 2021), whereas small- and medium-scale farms are prevalent in the cocoa and coffee sectors (Somarriba and López Sampson 2018; World Cocoa Foundation 2019). In the following subsections, we outline the approach and data used for analysing each of the four-pronged questions that we intend to address. Detailed methodologies are provided in the Supplementary Methods.

Global trade and consumption patterns of tropical crops

We used the UN Comtrade database (UN Statistics Division 2022) to estimate the annual quantity of imports and exports of oil palm, cocoa, and coffee for the period of 2011–2015 and 2016–2020. We focused on raw products, i.e. commodities in their raw form that undergo minimal processing. To give an estimate of the net demand for the production of a specific crop, the equivalent weight is used rather than the actual weight of the imported commodities recorded in the UN Comtrade database (see Table S1). For each crop, each country involved in the trade was classified based on their primary role as: (i) exporting country; (ii) trading country; and (iii) importing country. An exporting country is defined as a country whereby the quantities of commodity being exported far exceeds imports. A trading country is defined as a country whereby the quantities of commodities being exported account for more than 30% of the quantities being imported into the country; therefore, a large proportion of the commodity undergoes limited processing and then is exported elsewhere (Jones et al. 2020; Verschuur et al. 2022) An importing country is defined as a country where the quantities of imports far exceed exports. We evaluated patterns of consumption or utilisation of commodities across countries with differing economic statuses, i.e. high-income (HICs), upper-middle-income (UMICs), and low- and lower middle-income countries (LMICs). Consumption rates per capita were estimated as the cumulative quantity of raw commodities imported and the quantity produced in that country subtracted by the quantity exported, divided by the country's population.

Deforestation risk attributed to crop production

Deforestation risks attributed to crop production were estimated using three approaches: (A) forest cover change datasets in combination with data on the spatiotemporally explicit crop expansion data; (B) the latest spatial data on crop distribution; and (C) existing crude deforestation risks estimated from the sub-national data (Pendrill et al. 2022). The spatiotemporally explicit crop expansion data is considered to provide the most accurate direct attribution of the crop to deforestation, i.e. identification of forest clearance that was immediately replaced by the crop (Song et al. 2021). The latest spatial data on crop distribution provides an indirect attribution of the crop to deforestation, i.e. identification of forest clearance that eventually led to crop cultivation; such data is therefore considered more accurate than the crude estimates. For oil palm, we evaluated the deforestation risk in Indonesia and Malaysia. For cocoa, we focused on Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana, and for coffee on Brazil, Colombia, and Vietnam. Data types A, B, and C are available for oil palm; therefore, we used these three data types to generate and compare the embodied deforestation risk estimates. Data type A was unavailable for cocoa, so only data types B and C were used. For coffee, only data type C was available and therefore used in the analysis. We focused on the expansion of crops and deforestation occurring between 2011 and 2019, which reflects the period in which our different datasets overlap.

Trade agreements and the environmental sustainability elements

We collected data on trade agreements from the WTO RTA database (WTO 2022b) and focused on bilateral and multilateral (regional) trade agreements made between 1980 and 2022. For each trade agreement, we collected information on the RTA name, signatory countries, date of notification, date of entry into force, specific section(s) referencing the environment, environmental criteria relating to the traded products, and provision to withdraw trade preferences if the criteria are not met. The level of environmental commitments for each trade agreement was then assessed using an evaluative scale classified as very weak, weak, medium, and strong. These scales were generated based on four key criteria: (1) description of commitments to sustainable development and/or

environmental protection; (2) specific chapter dedicated to the environment, forest-based products, and/or biodiversity; (3) review of the environmental impact of the trade agreement; and (4) measures and support to address environmental issues. The characterisation of each criterion into different scales is summarised in Table 1.

Sustainability certification schemes' implementation and evidence of impact

For each commodity, we carried out a systematic review of past empirical studies evaluating the impact of sustainability certification schemes. Impact evidence was evaluated on five dimensions: (i) deforestation, biodiversity, or wildlife; (ii) greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions or fire; (iii) management of water, soil, or waste; (iv) poverty, income, or food security; and (v) human rights, tenure security, and conflicts. For each study, we collected information on: • the approach used to derive evidence, including: (i) case report or case-control study (either before-after or with-without), whether or not there was consideration of confounding factors, and (ii) rigorous quasi-experimental method, i.e. comparing treated and control before and after certification, and accounting for baseline conditions at the pre-treatment stage (Ferraro 2009; Sills et al. 2017); • whether or not the study considers the spatial spillover effects of certification schemes to the broader landscapes (within and surrounding certified farms) (Heilmayr et al. 2020; Schleicher et al. 2020); • the type of producer evaluated, including large-scale plantations, scheme smallholders (normally tied to plantations), or independent smallholders; and • indicators of sustainability evaluated on the five abovementioned dimensions and summary of their impact: positive, neutral (no impact), or negative.

Table 1. Categories of regional trade agreements (RTAs) made between 1980 and 2022 in terms of environmental elements and the characteristics of the associated clauses.

RTA Category (and number issued to date)	Broad characteristics of the environmental clauses				
	Description of commitments to sustainable development and/or environmental protection	Specific chapter dedicated to the environment, forest-based products and/or biodiversity	Review of the environmental impact of the trade agreement	Measures and support to address environmental issues	
Very weak (94 RTAs)	Minor <i>Most of these agreements contain only a brief reference to the environment or sustainable development. These agreements are limited to a minimal 'do no harm' approach, with many highlighting that environmental laws remain in the realm of national policy. Many include a general commitment to sustainable development, and a statement that it is inappropriate to relax environmental protections to attract investment or trade.</i>	No <i>None reference existing multilateral environmental agreements, and approximately half do not have a specific chapter dedicated to the environment. None contain specific sections on forest-based products or biodiversity.</i>	No <i>Most agreements include no review process for evaluating the environmental impacts of the trade agreement. Most of these agreements have minimum provisions for the right of each party to impose measures, if required, to protect animal and plant life and/or the right of each party to establish its own laws regarding the environment.</i>	No <i>The majority do not specify a particular environmental issue which should fall under protection or cooperation efforts.</i>	
Weak (79 RTAs)	Yes <i>These agreements contain more text than the 'very weak' agreements on their commitments to sustainable development and/or environmental</i>	Minor <i>Only some of the agreements contain specific sections on forest-based products and/or biodiversity, including commitments to</i>	No <i>Most agreements do not include review process for evaluating the environmental impacts of the trade agreement. Those</i>	No <i>Only some of the agreements mention specific areas for environmental cooperation. If they do, there is an</i>	

	<i>protection, as well as agreeing not to relax environmental protection to attract investment or trade. In addition, the agreements often reiterate their commitment to existing multilateral environmental agreements, and all include specific sections on the environment or trade and sustainable development.</i>	<i>combat illegal logging, promote sustainable forest management and take into account indigenous knowledge. They often also contain references to CITES (Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species), REDD+ (Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and forest Degradation), and the role of conservation, sustainable management of forests and enhancement of forest carbon stocks, but without going into any detail.</i>	<i>that do provide little meaningful or guaranteed public or civil society participation. Most agreements have minimum provisions for the right of each party to impose measures, if required, to protect animal and plant life and/or the right of each party to establish its own laws regarding the environment.</i>	<i>absence of detail on how this would be achieved beyond cooperation through existing forums and general mentions of capacity.</i>
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	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Medium (20 RTAs)	<i>These agreements contain detail commitments to sustainable development and/or environmental protection, as well as agreeing not to relax environmental protection to attract investment or trade.</i>	<i>These agreements contain specific chapters on the environment and/or trade and sustainable development, while most have multiple sections with an environmental focus.</i>	<i>Most of these agreements include both a government and civil society review mechanism of trade impact with the explicit aim of going beyond the more traditional tariff cuts and liberalisation of trade in goods, including new elements of environmental and labour issues.</i>	<i>Although most of the agreements include environmental impact review mechanism and committees, they do not include substantially more information on environmental issues and measures to address these than the agreements classified as 'weak'.</i>
Strong (2 RTAs)	<i>These agreements contain detail commitments to sustainable development and/or environmental protection, as well as agreeing not to relax environmental protection to attract investment or trade.</i>	<i>These agreements contain specific chapters on the environment and/or trade and sustainable development, and multiple sections with an environmental focus.</i>	<i>These agreements include both a government and civil society review mechanism of trade impact concerning environmental, labour, and human rights issues. These agreements contain a clause on biodiversity, recognising the importance of respecting and preserving traditional knowledge and the practices of indigenous communities, and promoting public participation on</i>	<i>These agreements contain a commitment not to fail to enforce environmental laws in ways that affect trade or investment between the parties. They contain procedures for each party to request consultations with the other regarding any matter arising under the environment chapter. They ensure transparency of domestic policies and measures pertaining to the traded products.</i>

<i>matters concerning biodiversity.</i>	<i>There are cooperative measures to improve and strengthen government sustainability standards and policies where applicable.</i>
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2.3 Results

What is the current global trade of tropical commodities and what are the commodity consumption patterns across countries with different development statuses?

Oil palm

Between 2016 and 2020, the largest exporting countries of raw oil palm were Indonesia, Malaysia, Colombia, and Guatemala (Fig. 1a). Indonesia and Malaysia exported 32.8 and 17.4 Mt per year, and Colombia and Guatemala exported 0.65 and 0.82 Mt per year, respectively. These countries are also the major producers of oil palm globally. The Netherlands was the major trading country importing 4.2 Mt per year of oil palm and 41.4% of these imports were then exported or distributed elsewhere. Middle-income Asian countries of India, China, and Pakistan, and high-income OECD countries of Germany, Spain, Italy, USA, and New Zealand were the largest importers of the commodity. Similar patterns of countries were obtained from 2011 to 2015 (Fig. S1a). The consumption rates per capita of oil palm in each country (accounting for the country's import, export, Table and crop production quantities), based on the 2016–2020 datasets, systematically vary by the country's economic status (Fig. 2a). HICs were the largest consumers of oil palm, with the median annual consumption rate of 4.44 kg per person. Comparatively, the median annual consumption of UMICs and LMICs was 3.54 and 2.96 kg per person, respectively. Consumption rates of New Zealand, the Netherlands, and Malaysia far exceeded those of other countries within the same economic status (Fig. 2a). New Zealand was estimated to consume 389 kg of oil palm per person per year, and the country's oil palm use had increased 126 times over the last two decades (Fig. S2a). New Zealand's oil palm consumption is primarily in the form of palm kernel meals to support the dairy and meat industries, which have grown rapidly in the last two decades (Stringer et al. 2016) and now account for 20% of the country's economy (Ballingall and Pambudi 2017). The Netherlands and Malaysia annually consume 141 and 158 kg of oil palm per person, on average, and consumption rates increased 3.6 and 1.7 times since the period of 1996–2000.

Cocoa

The largest exporting countries of cocoa between 2016 and 2020 were Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Indonesia, and Ecuador (Figs. 1b and S1b). Côte d'Ivoire exported nearly 2 Mt per year, whereas Ghana, Indonesia, and Ecuador exported 1.31, 0.97, and 0.33 Mt per year, respectively. EU countries of the Netherlands, Germany, France, and Spain, and Southeast Asian countries of Malaysia and Singapore were the major trading countries during this period. The Netherlands' imports of cocoa were 1.57 Mt per year and 47.5% of these imports were exported elsewhere. Germany's imports of cocoa were 1.33 Mt per year and 56.1% of these imports were exported elsewhere. High-income OECD countries of the USA, Belgium, UK, Italy, Canada, and Poland, and the middle-income country of Russia were the largest importers of the commodity. We obtained similar patterns from 2011 to 2015 (Fig. S1b). The consumption rates per capita of cocoa in each country, based on the 2016–2020 data, markedly vary by the country's economic status (Fig. 2b). HICs were the largest consumers of cocoa, with a median annual consumption rate of 1.06 kg per person. Comparatively, the median annual consumption of UMICs and LMICs were 0.23 and 0.02 kg per person, respectively. Cocoa

consumption of high-income European countries of Belgium, the Netherlands, Switzerland, and Iceland far surpassed that of other countries (Fig. 2a). Belgium was estimated to consume 64 kg of cocoa per person annually, on average, and the country's cocoa consumption had increased 5.3 times since the period of 1996–2000 (Fig. S21b). The Netherlands and Switzerland annually consume 48 and 24 kg per person, and cocoa consumption increased by a factor of 27 and 3.9 since the 1996–2000 period. Belgium and Switzerland are well known for their major chocolate production, and the Netherlands is the largest trade hub of cocoa beans in Europe (Alberts and Cidell 2006; Garrone et al. 2016).

Coffee

Between 2016 and 2020, the largest exporting countries of coffee were Brazil, Vietnam, Colombia, Indonesia, and Honduras (Figs. 1c and S1c). Brazil and Vietnam exported nearly 1.86 and 1.47 Mt per year, whereas Colombia, Indonesia, and Honduras exported 0.71, 0.36, and 0.34 Mt per year, respectively. Belgium was the largest trading country during this period, importing 0.3 Mt per year of coffee, and 62.9% of these imports were then exported elsewhere. High-income OECD countries of the USA, France, Germany, Italy, Canada, the UK, the Netherlands, Spain, Japan, and Austria were the largest importers of the commodity. Similar patterns were observed for the 2011–2015 period (Fig. S1c). Unlike oil palm and cocoa commodities whereby some countries play an important role as intermediaries or re-export hubs, coffee tends to be sourced directly from the producing countries (Figs. 1 and S1). Data from the 2016–2020 period show that HICs were the largest coffee consumers, with median consumption rates of 6.69 kg per person per year (Fig. 2c). The median consumption of UMICs and LMICs was significantly lower (0.97 and 0.01 kg per person per year, respectively). Coffee per capita consumption of high-income European countries of Luxembourg, Andorra, Iceland, Austria, Finland, Estonia, Norway, and France, and tropical tourist destination countries of Bermuda, Aruba, and Palau were far above that of other countries (Fig. 2c). Luxembourg and Andorra were estimated to annually consume 93 and 78 kg of coffee per person, on average, and the consumption rates had increased 77.5 and 3.8 times since the period of 1996–2000 (Fig. S2c). Iceland and Austria annually consume 47 and 35 kg of coffee per person, and consumption rates increased 2.5 and 5.9 times over the last two decades. Tropical tourist countries of Bermuda and Palau annually consume 37 and 29 kg of coffee per person, and the consumption rates have increased tremendously by a factor of 184 and 294 in the last two decades.

Figure 1 Global trade flow in raw oil palm (a), cocoa (b), and coffee (c) between 2016 and 2020. Raw is defined as a commodity in its raw form or with minimal processing, and thus it mostly contains the commodity. An exporting country is a country whereby exports of the commodity substantially exceed imports; an importing country is a country whereby imports substantially exceed exports; and a trading country is a country whereby exports of the commodity account for more than 35% of the imports (i.e. a large proportion of the commodity is transiting through the country and distributed elsewhere)

Figure 2 Country ranking in the per capita consumption of raw a oil palm (for food and non-food use), b cocoa, c and coffee between 2016 and 2020, by country economic status (i.e. HICs, UMICs, and LMICs). Per capita consumption in each country was estimated as the cumulative total quantity imported and total quantity produced in that country per year subtracted by the total quantity exported, divided by the country's population number

How is the production of tropical crops associated with deforestation, and how does the estimation of crop-induced deforestation vary by approach?

For oil palm, deforestation risk attributed to the crop was estimated based on three approaches with decreasing order of accuracy: (i) direct attribution of the crop to deforestation (based on spatiotemporal distribution of the crop), (ii) indirect attribution of the crop to deforestation (based on current spatial distribution of the crop), and (iii) crude deforestation estimates (based on country-level crop data; Pendrill et al. 2022). For Indonesia, the deforestation risk estimate based on the direct attribution approach (330,102 ha per year) was higher than those based on the indirect attribution (164,470 ha per year), but lower than those based on the crude estimate (424,757 ha per year) (Fig. 3a). For Malaysia, the deforestation risk estimate based on the direct attribution approach (157,117 ha per year) was higher than that based on the indirect attribution (79,190 ha per year) and the crude estimate (46,015 ha per year) (Fig. 3a). For cocoa, spatiotemporal explicit data were not available for the crop, and deforestation risks were estimated based on indirect attribution and crude approaches. Similar to Malaysian oil palm, deforestation risks based on the indirect attribution approach for cocoa were higher than those based on the crude estimates (Fig. 3b). The deforestation risk associated with the development of cocoa in Cote d'Ivoire was 37,250 ha per year based on the indirect attribution approach, whereas the crude approach estimated deforestation of 14,541 ha per year. For Ghana, the indirect attribution approach estimated a deforestation risk of 18,837 ha per year, whereas the crude approach estimated zero deforestation. For coffee, a detailed distribution map derived from satellite images is not available; therefore, deforestation risk can only be based on crude estimates. Based on this approach, the deforestation risk associated with the development of coffee in Colombia was 13,747 ha per year, and in Brazil and Vietnam approximately 1,300 ha per year (Fig. 3c).

Direct attribution and indirect attribution methods generally yielded a higher deforestation risk than the crude estimation approach twofold (Fig. 3a for oil palm in Malaysia and Fig. 3b for cocoa in Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana). An exception to this is oil palm in Indonesia, whereby the crude estimates were markedly higher than the direct attribution and indirect attribution methods (Fig. 3a). The underestimation of actual crop contribution to deforestation derived from the crude sub-country-level datasets for Côte d'Ivoire and Ghanaian cocoa is likely due to the predominance of smallholders in the production of these crop in these countries (Somarriba and López Sampson 2018; World Cocoa Foundation 2019), which makes the attribution of the crops to deforestation difficult to be accurately captured from the sub-national administrative data. On the other hand, the overestimation of actual crop contribution to deforestation derived from the crude sub-national-level datasets for Indonesian oil palm is likely due to the presence of multiple extractive industries (logging, timber plantations, and mining) in major oil palmproducing areas in Indonesia (Abood et al. 2015; Gaveau et al. 2019), potentially overlooking the contribution of other sectors to deforestation in the sub-national data.

Although oil palm has the highest deforestation risk in terms of the absolute deforestation extent (in ha per year), the percentage of forest loss attributed to the crop is smaller compared to cocoa (Fig. 3d, e). Based on the indirect attribution method, oil palm is associated with 1.5% forest loss in Indonesia between 2011 and 2019 (given forest extent of 99.7 million ha in 2011) and 3.8% forest loss in Malaysia (forest extent of 18.9 million ha in 2011) (Fig. 3d). Comparatively based on the same method, cocoa is associated with 8.5% forest loss in Cote d'Ivoire (given forest extent of 4 million ha in 2011) and 2.1% forest loss in Ghana over the same period (forest extent of 8 million ha in 2011) (Fig. 3e).

Figure 3 a–c Deforestation risk associated with the cultivation of oil palm, cocoa, and coffee, and **d–f** percent forest loss attributed to these commodities between 2011 and 2019 accounting for the extent of forest in 2011. Deforestation risk or percent forest loss is broken down by the approach used to derive the estimates with decreasing order of accuracy: (i) direct attribution, (ii) indirect attribution, and (iii) crude estimation approach. Major producing countries included in the assessment are Indonesia (IDN) and Malaysia (MYS) for oil palm; Côte d’Ivoire (CIV) and Ghana (GHA) for cocoa; and Brazil (BRA), Colombia (COL), and Vietnam (VNM) for coffee.

How have environmental clauses been incorporated into trade agreements and how effective are they in achieving the environmental goals?

Trade agreements aim to boost investments and commercial ties between participating countries by reducing or eliminating certain barriers to trade, such as reducing tariffs on products imported to a country. Import tariffs of goods across different countries had drastically reduced from an average of 14% before 1995 to 5% prior to 2020 (World Bank 2022), allowing easy movement of materials and goods over distant places. However, sending and receiving goods from one place to another also has implications for the redistribution of environmental costs along the production chain, and these costs are often unaccounted for in trade (Meng et al. 2018; Chen et al. 2021). The RTA database shows that more regional and bilateral trade agreements are being made, especially in the last three decades (Fig. 4a). Before 1990, there were three trade agreements signed per year on average globally, but the number increased to 15 per year in the period of 1991–2022.

Of all 512 trade agreements signed between 1980 and 2022, 195 agreements contain environmental clauses or references to environmental protection and/or sustainability (Table S2). These

environmental elements can be classified as: (i) very weak: these agreements contain only a brief reference to the environment or sustainable development; (ii) weak: these agreements contain more texts on a commitment to sustainable development and environment than the ‘very weak’ category, but still lack the details of the reviewing processes; (iii) medium: these agreements include a more substantial review of the impact of the agreement on sustainability, including the role of public participation in the review; (iv) strong: these agreements include a set of environmental criteria for defining the sustainability of the traded goods (Tables 1, S3).

We classified 94 of the 195 agreements as ‘very weak’ in terms of environmental commitments, 79 as ‘weak’, 20 as ‘medium’, and two as ‘strong’. The inclusion of environmental clauses in such agreements has become more common (Fig. 4b). After a decade since the period 2000–2009, ‘weak’ agreements displaced ‘very weak’ agreements as the most common category. ‘Medium’ and ‘strong’ agreements increased from only 9.5% in the period of 2010–2019 to 28.9% only in the last few years. Of those agreements classified as ‘medium’ or ‘strong’ between 2000 and 2022 (a total of 22), the majority (18) featured the EU and/or the UK as a party and the remaining four included the US, EFTA (European Free Trade Association), and Nicaragua–Taiwan.

Figure 4 Trends in a the likelihood of trade agreements signed per year between 1960 and 2021, and b the strength of environmental elements in trade agreements between 1980 and 2021. See Table 1 for the definition of the strength.

What is the evidence of sustainability standards’ effectiveness and impact?

Geographical and certification scheme coverage of past evaluations

A total of 51 studies of sufficient quality were found that evaluate the impact of sustainability certification for oil palm (Table S3; Fig. 5a). The majority of studies were carried out on the voluntary certification scheme RSPO (Roundtable on Sustainable Oil palm) (40 studies), and the remaining were on the national certification ISPO (Indonesian Sustainable Oil palm) and MSPO (Malaysian Sustainable Oil palm). Of these 51 studies, 41 were conducted in Indonesia and Malaysia and 8 in other countries (Thailand, Colombia, Ecuador, and Ghana). There was no study on other voluntary certification schemes supposedly important for oil palm, such as ISCC+(International Sustainability and Carbon Certification Plus) and RSB (Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials). This is probably because these schemes are not specific to oil palm and they are widely applied to other commodities and biofuel production and supply chains. A total of 25 studies were found for cocoa certification schemes, mostly focused on Côte d’Ivoire and Ghana (Table S4; Fig. 5b). These studies were carried out on farms certified by Rainforest Alliance Sustainable Agriculture (RA-SA), UTZ, or Fairtrade Cocoa schemes. For coffee certification schemes, we found significantly more studies than in cocoa (47 studies) (Table S4; Fig. 5c). A total of 27 studies were from countries in Latin America, 17 from countries in Africa, and 3 from Asia. Studies were carried out on farms certified by RA-SA, UTZ, Fairtrade, or 4C (The Common Code for the Coffee Community) schemes.

Agriculture production models and sustainability indicators evaluated

For oil palm sustainability certification, the evaluation studies found vary by producer type, i.e. plantations (including scheme smallholders) and independent smallholders (Fig. 5a). A large proportion of studies from Indonesia and Malaysia were derived from company plantations (32 out of 51 in total) and 19 were from independent smallholders. This could reflect the fact that key oil palm players in this region are large producers (Varkkey et al. 2018; Santika et al. 2021). On the other hand, studies on cocoa and coffee certification were all carried out on independent smallholders (typically under cooperative schemes) and medium-scale farms (Fig. 5b, c). This could reflect the majority of agricultural production models for these two crops globally (Somarriba and López Sampson 2018; World Cocoa Foundation 2019).

In terms of the sustainability indicators, studies for the oil palm certification schemes evaluated a wide range of sustainability dimensions, including deforestation and biodiversity, GHG emission, water and soil management, poverty, and human rights and land tenure conflicts (Fig. 5a). Studies appraising human rights or land tenure outcomes, as well as GHG emissions or fire, are more common in oil palm compared to cocoa and coffee (Fig. 5). The absence of human rights, land tenure, and conflicts appraisal for cocoa and coffee certification may be partly because the production model holders (Somarriba and López Sampson 2018; World Cocoa Foundation 2019). This is quite different from many oil palm production contexts, whereby large-scale plantations are key actors in major oil palm-producing countries, and the countries' weak land tenure systems often allow large-scale land acquisitions to occur leading to long-standing conflicts between agroindustry and local communities (CastellanosNavarrete et al. 2021; Yang and He 2021), thus making land tenure topics especially relevant for the crop. Nonetheless, human rights issues especially regarding child labour (i.e. workloads and deprived opportunities for health and education development as defined by ILO) and trafficking are recognised as pervasive issues in oil palm (Pasaribu and Vanclay 2021), cocoa (Perkiss et al. 2021), and coffee (Bager and Lambin 2020), regardless of the crop production model. The lack of GHG emission appraisal in cocoa and coffee is likely because cocoa and coffee are generally cultivated on mineral soil, unlike oil palm which has been extensively developed on peatland in the major producing countries of Indonesia and Malaysia (as part of government legacy in the utilisation of perceived "unproductive" land) (Dohong et al. 2017) and therefore making GHG emissions a highly relevant issue. Thus, the sustainability indicators covered by existing evaluations likely reflect specific challenges faced by each crop and the associated biophysical and socio-political contexts of the cultivated region.

Figure 5 Environmental and social impacts of sustainability certification for a oil palm, b cocoa, and c coffee, estimated from past studies. Studies are categorised based on: (i) the methodology used to derive evidence of impact: rigorous counterfactual versus case report or case-control approach; and (ii) the crop production model evaluated: large-scale plantations versus independent smallholders or mediumscaled farms.

Evidence of impact of sustainability certifications

Available evidence on the environmental and social impact of certification was largely drawn from case report or case-control approaches (comparing before and after, or with and without intervention, whether or not they address confounding factors). Of the total 51 studies we evaluated for oil palm, only a third (16 studies) applied a rigorous counterfactual approach (Fig. 5a), and nearly all of these were conducted on RSPO-certified plantations. For cocoa, a third of the studies (8 of 25) applied a counterfactual approach (Fig. 5b). For coffee, the proportion of studies applying a counterfactual approach was higher than for cocoa (51%) (Fig. 5c).

The impact of sustainability certification for oil palm appears to be mixed across different dimensions of sustainability (Fig. 5). The environmental impact of certification (deforestation and biodiversity, GHG emission, and water and soil management) was neutral or negligible, but the social impact (poverty, human rights, and land tenure) tends to be negative. For cocoa and coffee, the impact of certification tends to be positive on the environmental sustainability indicators. Certification impact on poverty and income appears positive for cocoa, but mixed (positive and neutral) for coffee.

2.3 Discussion and conclusions

A range of policy levers exist to achieve a reduction in the consumption and demand of tropical commodities. A broad distinction can be drawn between reform-oriented policy levers, which work through market-based mechanisms, and more transformative pathways (Acosta 2013; Martin et al. 2020). The likely effectiveness of different reform-oriented policy levers and the shift in political will required to achieve them vary. Broad normative economic proposals relating to degrowth in wealthy nations and enhanced sharing of wealth are put forward in ecological economics (Hickel 2020; Lenzen et al. 2022). These include practical proposals, such as cutting advertising industries to tackle consumption (Niinimäki et al. 2020; Sina et al. 2022), banning high environmental impact industries that have little value to society (e.g. private jets, large mansions) (Lynch et al. 2019), and eliminating planned obsolescence (Satyro et al. 2018; Bisschop et al. 2022). Degrowth scholars argue, however, that for poorer nations, growth is still necessary (Hickel 2021). Convivial conservation proposals call for more radical levers (Büscher et al. 2022). Below, we discuss some measures that fit within the deeper end of the reform-oriented spectrum and some that potentially could be classified as transformative in nature for tackling deforestation in supply chains, and more holistic visions of future pathways toward sustainability.

Reducing consumption of tropical commodities

Extractivism and neo-extractivism have long-standing roots in colonial and post-colonial development processes, in which tropical regions have been exploited for their natural resources and labour. Reformist proposals have focused on enhanced natural resource governance through conventional economic policies, which present environmental damage largely as a given (Acosta 2013). From this point of view, problems and conflicts that arise from extractivism can be solved with “proper governance” of how natural resources are used. The ways to achieve this are orthodox economic policies, such as increasing responsabilisation and participation of civil society in the oversight of extractive industry projects, more social investment in the areas where extractivism takes place to reduce social protests, and transparent information about the income obtained by the extractive enterprises, local governments, and central government. Environmental destruction is accepted as the inevitable cost of achieving development. Development paths that are inherently based on natural resource exploitation have critical implications for politics, social relations, and territorial orders, although these vary depending upon the willingness, for example, of political elites to support rent redistributions (Burchardt and Dietz 2014).

The sustainability of land and raw material use is increasingly challenged by over-exploitation, an increase in high-consumption lifestyles, and the unwillingness to target rich asset owners with taxes, and to deliver land reforms that tackle land inequalities (Burchardt and Dietz 2014). The extraction of raw materials has high environmental impacts, but their monetary value is significantly lower than that of processed goods (Frey et al. 2018; Givens et al. 2019). In the global system where places have unequal economic positions perpetuated by colonial histories (Ziai 2016), centres of consumption allow the exchange of values of materials through trade while undermining the productive potential of places where the raw materials are extracted. The accumulation of these value exchange activities allows centres of consumption to further extract raw materials and low-cost labour from the producing areas (Mair et al. 2016) and shift the environmental and social burden to the latter (Essandoh et al. 2020; Chen et al. 2021), consequently widening the social and economic disparities between places along the supply route (Mossay and Tabuchi 2015; Backhouse et al. 2021). It also distances economic agencies from territorial actors (Bonnedaahl et al. 2022).

The relationship between centres of consumption and producing areas can reflect the interconnection between high- and low/middle-income countries at the global scale under the current market system (Cai et al. 2018; Duan et al. 2021), as well as urban and rural areas (Sethi and Puppim de Oliveira 2015; Zhang et al. 2018), and general public and elite wealth within countries (Mirza et al. 2019; Beckert 2022). As our analysis shows, per capita consumption of forest-risk commodities for oil palm, cocoa, and coffee generally follows the country's socioeconomic status; countries with higher income are associated with higher consumption rates overall than countries with lower economic status (Fig. 2). Similar conclusions were found in other studies (Pendrill et al. 2019; Sun et al. 2022). Per capita consumption rates have increased over time for all country types, but they tend to race to the level where the highest consumption can be attained in a given period,

in this case by HICs (Fig. S1). The level of consumption by HICs can influence other countries by providing legitimisation to emulate a similar consumption trajectory, a behaviour analogue to the debate on historical greenhouse gas emission (GHG) expenditure (Wei et al. 2012; Jakob et al. 2021). Furthermore, HICs continue to make up the largest proportion of importing and trading countries in raw oil palm, cocoa, and coffee, whereas LMICs make up the largest proportion of exporting tropical countries (Fig. 1) where most of the environmental costs are incurred (Fig. 3) (Dupas et al. 2022).

Existing patterns of ever-growing consumption, deterioration of tropical environments driven by trade, and the widening of socioeconomic inequality will continue unless appropriate measures are implemented. HICs have the largest responsibility and capabilities to reduce their per capita consumption of forest-risk commodities (Tukker et al. 2020; Hickel et al. 2022). In the short term, one potential option to reduce the consumption of forest-risk raw commodities and their derivative products is to apply consumption taxes, whether they are produced domestically or imported (Afionis et al. 2017; Rocco et al. 2020). Raising commodity prices is likely not a popular approach for consumers, especially when the products have already been subjected to other taxes, such as the sugar tax on chocolate (Shahid and Bishop 2019). However, public acceptance may be higher if the revenue collected were recycled to support smallholder farmers and programmes in crop-producing countries to reduce environmental degradation due to crop cultivation. Several studies have shown that richer nations' consumers are willing to support activities linked to sustainable food production and consumption (Tait et al. 2016; Li and Kallas 2021). Alternatively, importing countries can apply import duties to forest-risk commodities and the revenue generated can be recycled to support producing countries' sustainable agricultural programmes and environmental monitoring and mitigation. Some HICs may have already been obliged to set zero or limited tariff rates for certain commodities due to bilateral or multilateral trade agreements (e.g. EU imports of cocoa from most African countries receive zero tariff), and increasing import duties would place them in violation of their commitment under the WTO. However, it may be unlikely that their exporting partners would initiate a dispute if they were receiving the revenue.

More ambitious transformative shifts in the food system and dietary behaviour towards more locally adapted food consumption patterns and minimising food waste are also required to reduce consumption rates in HICs (Green et al. 2015; Alexander et al. 2016; Hickel 2020) and urban areas in countries of emerging economies (da Costa Louzada et al. 2018; He et al. 2018). Public procurement is another key tool for incentivising more sustainable production (MartinOrtega and Treviño-Lozano 2023). There are also movements seeking to territorialise food and agricultural production as a whole, such as those supporting small-scale agriculture, agroecology principles, and reduced use of transgenic crops (Chaifetz and Jagger 2014). Such movements could receive more support from governments, e.g. through grant funding for food hubs or commoning institutions, such as Chambers of the Commons and Commons Assemblies, alongside land reform processes, which would represent deeper leverage points in richer nations with potential multi-dimensional benefits (Srnicek and Williams 2015).

Strengthening sustainability criteria in trade and a process of reform of environmental policy and land governance, and supporting improvement in producer country's own certification system

Meeting certain environmental criteria can be used to render a reduction in import duties described above. In general, WTO regulations, including the Technical Barriers to Trade Agreement, require criteria to be expressed based on performance rather than descriptive characteristics. Trade preference given to 'sustainable oil palm', for example, is permissible, but specifying 'sustainable oil palm' as only those products certified by RSPO, or other voluntary schemes, would not. HICs' government applying the measure would need to draw up a list of criteria for each forest-risk commodity which any supplier could potentially meet regardless of its membership in a certification scheme. These criteria can be informed by those listed in the existing voluntary standards. The use of voluntary certification schemes solely for trade preference is highly problematic due to several reasons. First, the existence and coverage of certification schemes vary widely, and some forest-risk commodities are either not covered or not to a great extent (Tayleur et al. 2017; van der Ven et al. 2018). Second, different certification schemes can cover different sets of criteria with different strengths in verification and auditing, and unintended consequences of 'standards shopping' may occur among suppliers (Schmeichel 2017). Third, past evaluations of the social and environmental impacts of voluntary certification schemes tend to show mixed results

which put into question their effectiveness (Fig. 5) (Oya et al. 2018; Meemken et al. 2021) and numerous complexities exist due to a mismatch in the implementation across different sectors and institutional levels (Lambin and Thorlakson 2018; Pacheco et al. 2020; Katic et al. 2023). Fourth, certification systems are often time-consuming and costly to introduce and implement and this can be particularly challenging for smallholder farmers (Dompereh et al. 2021; Watts et al. 2021).

Some voluntary standards organisations have made efforts to address the above-mentioned issues, e.g. through the development of specific smallholder standards with the provision of support for audits and streamlined processes for group certification (Latynskiy and Berger 2017; Watts et al. 2021) and jurisdictional or landscape approaches to demonstrating compliance with criteria such as zero deforestation across a wider area than individual farms (Seymour et al. 2020; Watts et al. 2021). However, there seems to be little progress in certification for providing traceability systems and verifying compliance with criteria throughout the supply chain (Pacheco et al. 2020; Meemken et al. 2021). Additionally, low/middle-income country governments have often been unenthusiastic or unreceptive to voluntary standards, as these are often perceived to be Western-dominated systems imposed on commodity supply chains without considering the development priorities of the countries that produce the commodities (Schouten and Bitzer 2015; Tyson and Meganingtyas 2022). This sentiment also partly lies behind the development of national schemes, such as ISPO and MSPO for oil palm (Astari and Lovett 2019; Choiruzzad et al. 2021).

Although the use of environmental criteria in trade is feasible, it should not be regarded as an ideal method in isolation, especially under the broader aim of life-enhancing economies. Trade agreements are not intrinsically well suited to pursuing socio-environmental outcomes, as they focus necessarily on the mutual removal of restrictions (such as import duties, quotas, and administrative requirements) rather than incentivising different modes of production, consumption, or investment, which is generally what environmental policy seeks to do (Gammage 2018; Kolcava et al. 2019; Bastiaens and Postnikov 2020). A combination of different forms of measures, including trade restrictions (e.g. discrimination in trade between products produced sustainably or unsustainably, either legally or illegally) coupled with a process of reform of environmental policy and land governance in the producing country partner, as well as a reward system for sustainably produced products in the consumer markets, all supported by capacity-building assistance from donor countries, is likely to be more effective than the current status quo. Where low/middle-income country governments have interest and can mobilise political will to achieve ambitious environmental goals, using trade restrictions could provide a valuable reinforcement, especially where the sustainability criteria can be met by certification or similar systems that have been developed by the producer country itself, rather than those of external voluntary sustainability standards. The provision of support from high-income consumer countries would be vital and could include assistance to improve the producer country's own certification system to ensure that it can credibly verify compliance with the criteria included in the agreement. In these circumstances, the inclusion of environmental criteria in trade agreements could play a valuable role. Nevertheless, regular and robust monitoring and evaluation will be required to assess both the direct and indirect impacts of these initiatives so that timely and adequate action can be taken to minimise the unintended effects (Sellare et al. 2022; Zhunusova et al. 2022).

Enhancing monitoring of crop environmental footprints through detailed spatiotemporal data

Efforts to monitor deforestation associated with commodity production have so far focused on industrial-scale plantations (e.g. oil palm and soybean), and this is mainly due to their social and environmental consequences (Fehlenberg et al. 2017; Phélinas and Choumert 2017; Santika et al. 2019) and the ease of capturing large-scale land cover change from satellite images. The impact of crop expansion by small-scale farmers has received less attention, although there have been growing calls for more rigorous monitoring (Ashiagbor et al. 2022; Ramírez-Mejía et al. 2022; Zhao et al. 2022). Elevated demands for tropical crops from the global market can incentivise lucrative practices and maximisation of production in the short term, and this likely has an impact on the exacerbation of agricultural expansion by both large-scale and small-scale producers following numerous mechanisms and pathways. Studies from Indonesia indicate that large-scale plantations were the primary actor in the expansion of oil palm in remote forest lands in the early stage of oil palm development; however, following the establishment of oil palm mills in the new development areas, the number of smallholders began to grow at rapid rates emulating the earlier expansion patterns of the large-scale producers, creating an extremely complex supply chain network

(Prabowo et al. 2017; Heilmayr et al. 2020; Santika et al. 2021). Studies from the coffee sector in Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire show that lack of agricultural input and management due to limited capital in smallholders poses challenges to poor soil fertility and high pest and disease pressures, and this aggravates the abandonment of farms that are no longer productive on the seeking of new fertile lands and forest areas for agriculture (Ameyaw et al. 2018; Ashiagbor et al. 2022).

Our study shows that the widely used approach based on rudimentary data on crop distribution at the national or sub-national level tends to underestimate the crop deforestation risk attributed to both large-scale plantations and smallholder farms (Fig. 3). Detailed spatiotemporal change in land cover derived from satellite images that enable the detection and differentiation between large-scale plantations and small-scale farms can offer more accurate monitoring (Bey et al. 2020; Xu et al. 2020). Coupled with the trade datasets, they can be used to inform environmental policy measures. Nonetheless, while revealing the impact of deforestation on global supply chains is key for all actors, the availability of more information and traceability should not distract from the aim to catalyse change in the basic features of capitalist relations towards identifying and pursuing more transformative leverage points.

Potential transformative leverage points in achieving socio-ecological goals in supply chains

Current work on transformative change levers seeks to identify leverage points as possible entry points to a system to make far-reaching changes (Meadows 1999). In food and agricultural systems, transformations are increasingly called for in policy circles, including tackling deforestation, but the primary question is how to achieve such shifts given the power inequalities and concentrations of wealth within agrifood systems (Dupas et al. 2022; Slater et al. 2022). Neoliberal economic globalisation has given rise to multinational corporate power, expansion of global value chains, and polycentric trade patterns, rendering communities and national governments less power than before to hold multinational companies to account (Sikor and Lund 2009; Clegg et al. 2018). Actors who hold such power are increasingly able to influence the rules governing the global economy in their interests, leading to a thinning of democracy and a shrinking of civic space (Standing 2018). A recent intergovernmental assessment from IPBES urgently calls for a moderation of market fundamentalism, privatisation, accumulation, and extraction, and amplification of solidarity and ethics of care (IPBES 2019).

Measures such as import duties, environmental due diligence, and sustainability standards may be easier for governments to contemplate in the short to medium term, but this is fundamentally because such measures are relatively unchallenging to incumbent actors and relations in the global political economy. Evidence of the impact of sustainability standards is mixed (Oya et al. 2018; Schleifer and Sun 2020; Garrett et al. 2021) and trade agreements are rarely the best option to achieve socio-environmental goals (Rodrik 2018; Kehoe et al. 2020), and to some extent, they can be seen as a distraction from more transformative approaches (Martin et al. 2020). Given the fundamental limitations of market-based mechanisms, it is valuable to ask what a wider range of responses might entail that can facilitate meaningful transformative change to tackle deforestation and all other supply chain sustainability challenges, given that such challenges essentially share the same root cause.

Huge distances created between local dwellers in a landscape and those with control over it, by commodity trade relations, are problematic in terms of creating accountability and an ethics of care. Values, mindsets, attitudes, and feelings of connectedness to nature fundamentally shape the goals that determine land uses, and conversely, a sense of detachment has causally contributed to the deforestation affected by actors locally and extra-territorially (Brown et al. 2019; Bonnedahl et al. 2022). Uncoupling global value chains is needed to lessen the social and environmental costs (Akizu-Gardoki et al. 2018; Lenzen et al. 2022), although some trade will still be needed for food security reasons. Some commodities consumed in the Global North, such as horticultural crops, may be grown locally (López Cifuentes and Gugerell 2021; Li et al. 2022), while for other commodities, especially those with highly negative effects, there may be potential for substitutions (Green et al. 2015; BlayPalmer et al. 2018). Understanding the potential pathways for uncoupling requires not only detailed scientific analyses of trade-offs, but also a broader exploration of potential value shifts and pathways to greater sustainability through post-growth scenarios (Hickel 2020; Lenzen et al. 2022).

There is a need to move beyond approaches that present sustainable supply chain issues, including deforestation, as fundamentally an issue relating to production zones, and instead, focus on the root causes of the problem. Attentiveness to different classes in society is needed, addressing their relative levels of responsibility and accountability for biodiversity losses, environmental degradation, and climate change (Büscher et al. 2022; Green and Healy 2022). Some actors have greater power in the broader structures of capitalist accumulation. Conservation initiatives not only need to give local people a central role as decision-makers in planning (Friedman et al. 2020; Carmenta et al. 2023), but also focus on behavioural change efforts to create greater democracy in larger structures of power which ultimately shape the success of local-scale initiatives (Büscher et al. 2022; Corson and Campell 2023). Attention has been focused on sourcing localities for far too long, and ultimately this lens depoliticises analytic diagnoses of sustainability challenges (Brockhaus et al. 2021; Kumeh and Ramcilovic-Suominen 2023). Refocusing attention on higher-scale concentrations of power and wealth and how to disrupt and overcome these is therefore key. This could be attained through radical policy prescriptions, such as debt cancellation for poorer nations that were colonised, taxing agro-commodity companies to internalise their social and environmental impacts, increased regulation, monitoring, and accountability of corporate impacts in deforestation-risk countries, as well as support for locally designed approaches which strengthen autonomy.

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Data availability All data used in this study were obtained from public repositories and are described in the cited references. Data on the systematic review and the strength of environmental provisions in trade agreements are included in the Supplementary Information of this article.

Declarations

Conflict of interest We declare that we have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Santika, T., Nelson, V., Hagggar, J., & Thushari, I. (2025). Trade agreements and environmental provisions: a counterfactual analysis of environmental impact shifting under global economic inequality. *Global Environmental Change*, 93, 103028.

Abstract

Regional trade agreements (RTAs) have proliferated in recent decades, with increasingly stringent environmental clauses aimed at mitigating trade impacts. However, studies on the environmental effects of RTAs typically focus on a few agreements and indicators, hindering a comprehensive understanding of their effects across various resources. Additionally, the long-term effectiveness of environmental provisions within RTAs remains unclear. To address this gap, we applied a rigorous counterfactual analysis to evaluate changes in multiple resource footprints associated with RTAs and environmental provisions across 195 countries annually from 1990 to 2018. We examined four key resources: primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use. Findings revealed that RTAs were linked to the outsourcing of environmental footprints across all resource types while reducing footprint insourcing, a phenomenon known as environmental impact shifting. This effect was particularly evident in wealthier countries, where outsourcing of primary energy, primarily from lower-income nations, rose by 11.6%, raw materials by 13.6%, and land use by 33.5%, compared to similar non-RTA countries. Furthermore, these countries' insourcing of primary energy was reduced by 48.3% and blue water by 15.4% relative to non-RTA counterparts. Environmental provisions within RTAs had limited long-term effectiveness in reducing environmental footprints outsourcing. Global trends show a growing disparity in resource use between wealthy and poor countries, exacerbated by RTAs. Rigorous footprint accounting and a resource-equity mechanism, including ecological premiums for resource-intensive imports, are essential within RTAs. Wealthier nations must adopt more accountable consumption-based governance, prioritising reductions in material consumption to alleviate the socio-ecological impacts on poorer countries.

Keywords: Blue water, Footprints, Land use, Primary energy, Raw materials, Sustainability

3.1 Introduction

International trade is widely seen as crucial for global prosperity (OECD, 2023; The World Bank, 2018). The dominant view in global policy circles is that economic growth is necessary to finance development and transitions to environmental sustainability, e.g. decarbonisation. However, this perspective is also extensively criticised in terms of the problematic relationship between trade, economic growth, inequality, and planetary environmental boundaries and cascading tipping points (Franzke et al., 2022; Humpenoder et al., 2022), as well as differential responsibilities for the socio-ecological impacts of trade. Trade has played a key role in economic globalisation of the twentieth century, and the number of Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) have proliferated in recent decades. RTAs are reciprocal trade agreements between two or more partner states aiming to reduce tariffs (import and export duties) and/or other trade barriers between the parties. RTAs constitute one of the allowed exemptions from the World Trade Organisation's (WTO's) core principle of non-discrimination between trading partners, though they are subject to a number of WTO requirements for notification and transparency. As of February 2024, a total of 365 Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) are in effect, encompassing arrangements such as Free Trade Agreement (FTA), Customs Union (CU), Economic Integration Agreement (EIA), and Partial Scope Agreement (PSA) (World Trade Organization, 2024).

Numerous studies have explored the societal and environmental impacts of trade (Friel et al., 2020; Roux et al., 2021; Wiedmann and Lenzen, 2018), but much less has been carried out specifically on the environmental impacts of RTAs. Existing research tends to concentrate on a limited number of RTAs (Nemati et al., 2019) and emphasises economic outcomes, such as trade volumes (Kohl, 2014; Nguyen, 2019) and investment flows (Duong et al., 2021; Larch and Yotov, 2024), revealing that RTAs often boost imports in participating countries and However, there is a lack of comprehensive assessments of RTAs' resource footprints, the social and environmental costs, associated with traded goods. Most studies focus on isolated indicators, such as deforestation, pollution, or carbon emissions (Abman and Lundberg, 2020; Le et al., 2016; Nemati et al., 2019), and typically find that RTAs exacerbate pollution and emissions in less affluent producing countries (Halicioglu and Ketenci, 2016; Nemati et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2022). The outsourcing of resource-intensive production to these nations frequently results in environmental degradation and social inequities, often due to inadequate governance structures (Le et al., 2016; Suarez-Varela and Rodríguez-Crespo, 2022). Understanding the socioenvironmental costs of RTAs across numerous resource indicators is crucial, since ignoring them may perpetuate socio-ecological exploitation and hinder progress toward achieving global sustainability and climate change mitigation objectives (Baccini, 2019; Felbermayr et al., 2024; Friel et al., 2020; Tian et al., 2022).

Social and environmental provisions in RTAs are a mechanism designed to mitigate negative 58 impacts of trade agreement or to strengthen positive ones (Mattoo et al., 2020). These provisions have 59 become more stringent in recent years (Blümer et al., 2020; Morin et al., 2018). While some see potential 60 in such provisions (Berger et al., 2020; Brandi and Morin, 2023; Kehoe et al., 2020), there has been a 61 lack of thorough evaluation on their effectiveness (Brandi et al., 2020). Previous studies have either 62 contrasted the presence of environmental provision to its absence (Abman et al., 2024; Hoekman et al., 63 2023), covered only key countries (<60 of OECD and major developing nations) (Baghdadi et al., 2013; Martinex-Zarzaso and Oueslati, 2018; Yuan et al., 2023) been limited to a single environmental measure 65 (Abman et al., 2024; Martínez-Zarzaso and Oueslati, 2018; Yu et al., 2024; Yuan et al., 2023), or been 66 based on outdated data (before 2011) (Baghdadi et al., 2013; Bastiaens and Postnikov, 2017; Martínez67 Zarzaso and Oueslati, 2018; Zhou et al., 2017). The findings of these studies are mixed. Some indicate a 68 decline in imports of environmentally harmful commodities (such as steel, cement, or chemicals) (Brandi 69 et al., 2020) or a reduction in the environmental impact following the adoption of RTAs with environmental provisions (Yu et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2017), while others report marginal effects (Presberger and 71 Bernauer, 2023; Sorgho and Tharakan, 2022). Notably, none of these studies have investigated the 72 influence of such provisions over an extended period beyond the second year of adoption. Given that 73 environmental provisions are often highlighted as a crucial strategy for reducing trade-related 74 environmental impacts (Bellmann and Bulatnikova, 2022; Berger et al., 2020), it is crucial to assess their 75 potential effectiveness over the long term.

To address the limits of earlier research, here we present novel comprehensive assessment of the global use and exchange of natural resources embodied in traded goods in relation to RTAs and the strength of environmental provisions across 195 nations annually between 1990 and 2018. We examined a range of key resource footprints: primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use. We evaluated the impact of environmental provisions in RTAs on footprints up to four years after adoption, providing a clearer understanding of how impacts vary over time. We sought to answer three related questions: (1) What are the trends in resource footprints and trade globally, regardless of RTA, including patterns of footprints overall and by resource origin (insourced vs outsourced), and the socioeconomic features of the trading countries? (2) How do RTAs affect countries' footprints, either those outsourced or insourced? (3) Do stronger environmental clauses in RTAs reduce the outsourcing of footprints by countries, and is this effect sustained in the long term? For resource footprints, we utilised the recently developed and currently most comprehensive multi-regional input-output data GLORIA (Global Resource Input-Output Assessment) (Lenzen et al. 2022). For the strength of environmental provisions within RTAs, we used recent data by Santika et al. (2024).

In addition to broadening the scope of previous research, we employed a rigorous counterfactual analysis to evaluate the impact of RTAs and environmental provisions. Specifically, we employed a difference-in-differences (DID) regression coupled with non-parametric matching method (Fig. 1). Although this approach is commonly used to evaluate the effectiveness of development programs,

it has rarely been applied to assess the impacts of RTAs (Abman et al., 2024; Nie et al., 2022). The 'counterfactual' assesses the potential trade flow outcomes for countries in the absence of an RTA by comparing the actual trade flows observed under the RTA with those of a control group that does not participate in an RTA. Given that countries engaged in specific RTA arrangements may differ in key characteristics (e.g., GDP, geographical location) from those that are not, it is essential to account for these differences through matching to allow apples-to-apples comparisons. Using matching, we were able to investigate variations in RTAs' impact on environmental footprints among nations with varying economic statuses. Because RTAs were implemented at different times, and various signatory countries may have joined or left at different stages (e. g. EU enlargement and Brexit), it is crucial to match these countries to specific control groups and time periods for incorporation into the DID analysis. This method also allows us to investigate how the effects of RTAs and their environmental provisions evolve over time after their implementation.

3.2 Theory

The theoretical framework underpinning our study builds upon three interconnected themes: (1) the environmental footprints of countries in the context of global economic inequality; (2) the influence of trade liberalisation through RTAs on these distributional dynamics; and (3) the influence of environmental clauses in RTAs in reshaping or reinforcing these patterns

Footprints in territorial versus global systems under inequality

In policy analysis and economics, great attention is paid to the relationship between economic development and the environment. A widely used framework for this inquiry is the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) (Beckerman, 1992; Panayotou, 1993). It posits an inverted U-shaped relationship between economic growth and environmental degradation, with environmental degradation increases during the initial stages of economic development but decreases once a country attains higher income levels and can invest in cleaner technologies and adopt more efficient environmental regulations (Dasgupta et al., 2006; Panayotou, 1993). However, a key assumption of this theory is that environmental impacts are primarily contained within territorial borders (relying on production-based accounting) and overlooking both global interdependence and inequality (Kaika and Zervas, 2013; Makarov and Alatas, 2024). Empirical analyses show that increasing wealth and consumer demand frequently result in the outsourcing of environmental resources (Haberl et al., 2023; Peters et al., 2021).

Consumption-based accounting, which track environmental impacts beyond national borders, the EKC hypothesis is facing growing scrutiny (Bagliani et al., 2008; Makarov and Alatas, 2024). Research reveals that in an unequal globalised economy, many high-income countries shift a large share of their environmental burdens onto lower-income nations (Fu et al., 2023; Hertwich, 2021; Liu et al., 2017). At the global level, this undermines the EKC's better promise that economic growth leads to reduced environmental degradation. These findings challenge the EKC's optimistic narrative by showing that environmental pressures are not necessarily alleviated through growth, but merely displaced. Taking this into account, our first hypothesis is therefore: H1: As countries develop economically, their resource consumption increases, with high-income nations offshoring a significant portion of their environmental footprints overseas

Figure 1 Counterfactual analysis framework applied in this study. Difference-in-differences (DID) coupled with non-parametric matching method used to evaluate: (a) the effect of RTA on the change in footprint outsourcing (IRF) of countries, (b) the effect of RTA on the change in footprint insourcing (DRF) of countries, and (c) the effect of the stringency of environmental provisions in RTAs (“strong” or “medium” provisions versus “weak”, “very weak” or no provisions) on the change in footprint outsourcing (IRF) of countries two years after the RTA implementation. Positive value for the DID implies that the RTA or environmental provision was associated with an increase in outsourcing or insourcing of footprint compared to control, whereas negative value implies a decrease. Resource footprint indicators evaluated include the primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, refer to the web version of this article.

Trade liberalisation through RTAs and footprint dynamics

RTAs are key to international trade. By reducing or removing tariffs and non-tariff barriers between participants, RTAs lead to the promotion of more integrated and wider-reaching transnational

transactions. Yet, their influence extends beyond just trade volumes, as they significantly reconfigure the geographical and environmental impacts of production, consumption, and resource utilisation. Studies have shown that through this preferential market access mechanism, RTAs promote specialisation on the basis of comparative advantage that leads to significant supply chain reconfiguration as industries move to countries that can offer cost efficiencies, favourable infrastructure, or regulatory lax (Anderer et al., 2020; Antras and Staiger, 2012; Osgood, 2018). In many cases, these encourage outsourcing of resource- and emission-intensive industries (Dellachiesa and Myint, 2016; Tian et al., 2022).

The environmental impact of RTAs often depends on the economic strength and institutional capacity of the countries involved, two factors that are typically intertwined. The pathways through which these effects unfold are outlined in Fig. 2a. In developed economies, RTAs often improve domestic environmental outcomes due to strong institutions, public demand for environmental standards, and multilateral cooperation, although they can also shift emissions abroad (Jonsson et al., 2023; Kolcava et al., 2019; Wang and Kuusi, 2024). In contrast, low-income countries frequently face challenges in realising these benefits, as weak institutions, limited access to clean technologies, and a focus on short-term economic growth can undermine the implementation of rigorous environmental regulations (de LT Oliveira and Hecht, 2017; Zografos and Robbins, 2020). Consequently, they may experience greater environmental harm, such as resource overexploitation, expansion of polluting industries, and continued dependence on high-emission sectors. Considering this, our second hypothesis is therefore: H2: The environmental effects of RTAs vary by economic status, with high-income countries gaining the most. These nations can improve their domestic footprint while shifting more resource-intensive activities to poorer countries

RTA's environmental clauses further reshape footprint dynamics

Given mounting concerns about the environmental impacts of trade liberalisation, RTAs are increasingly incorporating environmental provisions into their agreements. These clauses aim to balance economic integration with ecological sustainability by putting in place measures to prevent or reduce environmental damage linked to expanded trade. However, their effectiveness varies with the strength of the provisions, as illustrated in Fig. 2b. Studies show that weak clauses act often as diplomatic tokens rather than real commitments, providing little protection against environmental harm (Jinnah and Morgera, 2013). On the other hand, strong and enforceable environmental measures, especially those with clear legal responsibilities and oversight, can help prevent the weakening of environmental regulations in the short term (Bastiaens and Postnikov, 2017). In some cases, these measures promote broader institutional reforms beyond the environmental domain (Kim, 2012; Postnikov and Bastiaens, 2014). Over time, these provisions can contribute to lasting environmental standards, provided there is sustained engagement from civil society (Marslev and Staritz, 2023; Tran et al., 2017)

Nevertheless, in the long-term, the real-world effectiveness of even the strongest clauses can be undermined by the adaptive strategies of both states and corporations. Studies have shown that companies can engage in regulatory arbitrage by relocating operations to countries with weaker enforcement, or resort to greenwashing by adopting surface-level environmental initiatives to conceal unsustainable practices (Nikou, 2025; Yang et al., 2020). Multinational corporations can further complicate matters by exploiting legal loopholes, restructuring supply chains, or using subsidiaries to avoid environmental responsibilities (Duan and Jiang, 2021; Ma et al., 2023). Moreover, the disjunction between top-down regulations and ground-level realities in producer countries can give rise to isomorphic mimicry, where institutions adopt the appearance of compliance without substantive change, thus reducing environmental laws to symbolic rather than transformative instruments (Kourtellis, 2021; Ye, 2020). Trade enforcement can also become politically sensitive when major allies are involved, as economic interdependence often deters punitive actions (Chen and Evers, 2023). Considering these dynamics, and the persistence of elevated global demand driven by affluent consumers, our third hypothesis is therefore: H3: While strong environmental clauses in RTAs can help reduce the outsourcing of environmental footprints in the short term, their effectiveness may diminish over the long term.

Figure 2 Theoretical pathways linking RTAs and environmental provisions to environmental outcomes. The causal mechanisms through which: (a) RTAs affect environmental performance in signatory countries across different levels of economic development (supporting hypothesis H2), and (b) environmental provisions in RTAs affect short- and long-term environmental outcomes (supporting hypothesis H3).

3.3 Methods

Data

which include bilateral and multilateral trade agreements, and the strength of environmental provisions; (2) natural resource consumption and the flow of resource footprints between countries globally; and (3) country socioeconomic and geographical characteristics, such as GDPs, development status, total human population over time, physical locations, and regional membership. The source of these data and the references supporting their use in our analysis are provided in Appendix A.

RTA data were obtained from the World Trade Organisation's (WTO) Regional Trade Agreements Database (2024). The data include all 634 trade agreements signed since 1948, as well as key information such as the RTA name, status (inactive, in force, or early announcement), date of signature, date of entry into force, bilateral or multilateral status, and signatory countries (including the original and current signatories). In this study, we analysed 420 RTAs from 1990 to 2018, encompassing all trade arrangements (FTA, CU, EIA, and PSA). Data on the strength of environmental provision in RTAs during the same period were obtained from a recent study by Santika et al. (2024), which are provided as supplemental materials in the relevant publication. The environmental provisions in each trade agreement were evaluated according to expert evaluations on a scale of very weak, weak, medium, and strong. These scales were developed based on four key criteria: (1) a description of the commitments made to environmental protection and/or sustainable

development; (2) a special chapter dedicated to the environment, forest products, and/or biodiversity; (3) a review of the trade agreement's environmental impact; and (4) measures and support to address environmental issues. 'Very weak' RTAs are categorised as those that include minimal elements of criteria 1. 'Weak' RTAs are those that satisfy criteria 1 and at least some components of criteria 2. 'Medium' RTAs are those that fulfil criteria 1 through 3, while 'strong' RTAs meet all four criteria. A summary of the evaluation of each criterion into different scales is shown in Table S1 in the Supplementary Information.

Data on natural resource use and the transfer of resource footprints across countries were acquired from the UNEP-supported SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024). The database was built on the GLORIA (Global Resource Input-Output Assessment) model (Lenzen et al., 2022, 2017), and it is the most extensive MRIO (Multi-Region Input-Output) database to date, involving resource consumption and flows between 195 nations worldwide, providing a complete estimate of a country's consumption footprints from domestic sources (insourcing) and those imported (outsourcing). The SCP-HAT database provides yearly data from 1990 to 2018. While the database contains multiple indicators of resource footprints and impacts, we focused on four of them for this study, including primary energy (in joules), raw materials (in tonnes), blue water (in cubic meters), and land use (in hectares). Country-level statistics on socioeconomic indicators, such as the annual change in GDP per capita and economic status from 1990 to 2019, were obtained from the World Bank database (2024). The economic status of a country is classified into four categories: high-income countries (HICs), upper-middle-income countries (UMICs), lower-middle-income countries (LMICs), and low-income countries (LICs). The change in total human population in each nation over the same period was acquired from the UN Population Division Data Portal (2023). Each country's physical location was represented by the geographical position of its capital city, with data collected from the World Cities database. The data were used to calculate the distance between nations in terms of trade. Although commodities can enter and exit a nation from a variety of locations, a vast majority of operations are likely to take place close to the capital. Data on nation regional membership was obtained from the UN Statistics Division (2023), which includes five broad regions: Africa, America, Asia, Europe, and Oceania.

Analysis

Our analyses were organised into three main themes, which corresponded to the three study objectives (and the corresponding hypotheses) that we sought to address. The analytical approaches we used for each theme is described below and were investigated for all four resource types: primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use.

Trends in resource consumption and trade globally, regardless of RTA

The first research objective was to assess hypothesis H1, specifically: (1a) the patterns of natural resource consumption in different countries globally, irrespective of resource origin; (1b) the patterns of natural resource consumption by resource origin (insourced vs. outsourced); and (1c) the patterns of resource outsourcing of countries in relation to the socioeconomic characteristics of the trade participants. The hypothesis underlying each assessment, along with supporting references and the datasets utilised for evaluation, is summarised in Table A1 in Appendix A.

Evaluation 1a.

To conduct evaluation 1a, we used the SCP-HAT consumption data as well as country-level human population and economic status data. We undertook a descriptive analysis by visualising the yearly change in per capita resource consumption from 1990 to 2018, separated by country economic level (HICs, UMICs, LMICs, and LICs). To estimate the trends in resource consumption per capita over time for each country's economic level j , we fitted an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to the log scaled data, i.e. $\log(RF_{i,t,j}) = \alpha_{0,j} + \alpha_{1,j}YEART$, for $\forall j \in \{HICs, UMICs, LMICs, LICs\}$ (1) where $RF_{i,t,j}$ denotes the overall per capita resource footprints (regardless of origin) of country i belonging to economic level j at time t , $YEART$ denotes the year at time t , and $\alpha_{0,j}$ and $\alpha_{1,j}$ are the OLS model parameters to be estimated for each country's economic level j . To show the global fair share of resource use, we additionally computed the average consumption rates worldwide for each year

Evaluation 1b

To undertake evaluation 1b, we also used the SCP-HAT and country-level human population and income status data. A descriptive analysis was performed by visualising the per capita resource consumption by country's economic level, total vs those outsourced, for three time periods from 1990 to 2018

Evaluation 1c

To undertake evaluation 1c, we used the SCPHAT data as well as country-level statistics on human population, GDP model to analyse per capita resource outsourcing, considering the GDPs of both the home and outsourced countries, the geographical distance between them (Chaney 2018), and the year to account for global events potentially influencing trade (e.g., wars) (Zhu et al., 2024). We fitted a semi-parametric Generalised Additive Model (GAM) (Hastie, 2017) with a smoothing function to the data (in log scale), i.e. $\log(\text{IRFi,j,t}) = f_1(\text{YEAR}_t) + f_2(\text{GDPCi,t}) + f_3(\text{GDPOi,j,t}) + f_4(\text{DISTi,j})$ (2) IRFi,j,t represents the per capita resource outsourcing of country i to country j at time t , YEAR_t denotes the year variable. GDPCi,t represents the per capita GDP of home country i at time t , while GDPOi,j,t represents the per capita GDP of outsourced country j as a partner of country i at time t . DISTi,j represents the distance between home country i and outsourced country j . Lastly, f denotes the smoothing function estimated by the GAM

The effect of RTAs on countries' footprints, whether outsourced or insourced

The second research objective sought to evaluate hypothesis H2 or the effect of RTA participation on the resource footprints of nations, specifically those that were (2a) outsourced, or (2b) insourced. The intervention under evaluation is RTA participation. Table A2 presents a summary of the hypotheses underlying each assessment, accompanied by corresponding references and the datasets employed for their evaluation

Evaluation 2a

To conduct evaluation 2a, we used the RTA data, SCP-HAT consumption statistics, country-level human population, GDP, and economic status, as well as distance between countries. We applied a DID approach with matching to compare changes in footprint outsourcing between pair of countries before and after an RTA went into effect, to those in which the countries did not have an RTA. We ensured that the GDPs of the country pairs, their distance, the years when the change in footprints was analysed, and the baseline footprint outsourcing before RTA signing were all comparable. The analytical framework is illustrated in Fig. 1a, with each step explained below. Step 1. Create pools of treated and control units from the data. We initially filtered the SCP-HAT data to include only countries that outsource their resource footprints to others. For the treatment group, we selected pairs of trading countries that had implemented an RTA for two years. The control group consisted of pairs of countries that did not have an RTA during the same period. Step 2. Find a matched control for each treated unit. For each treated unit, we identified a matching case from the control group that shared the same home country but had a different outsourcing partner. We ensured that the partner had similar characteristics to the treated unit, including GDP, geographical proximity to the home country, and the extent of outsourcing three years before. We applied nearest neighbour matching with replacement by simulating various calliper width to achieve sufficient covariate balance between the treated and control units across all relevant covariates. Step 3. Estimate the RTA effect on the matched dataset. We fitted an OLS model to the matched dataset to estimate the impact of RTA on the change in countries' footprint outsourcing (in log scale), i.e. $\log(\text{IRF}_2) - \log(\text{IRF}_{-1}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{TA}$ (3) IRF_2 denotes the extent of footprint outsourcing two years following RTA implementation, while IRF_{-1} denotes the extent of outsourcing a year before the RTA came into force. TA denotes a binary variable representing the treatment (RTA) and control (no RTA) status. A significantly positive β_1 value indicates that countries with RTAs are associated with greater outsourcing of footprints compared to those without RTAs, while a significantly negative value suggests the opposite. In addition to evaluating the overall impact of RTAs, we also explored the heterogeneity of RTA effects across countries with varying economic levels, including HICs, UMICs, and LMICs and LICs jointly. Step 4. Perform robustness checks. We employed diagnostic tests to assess the quality of the matching, including examining the density distribution of the treated and control units before and after matching (Fig. S1), quantifying the standardised mean differences (SMD) between the treated and control units of the post-match data (Table S2), and the bias reduction from the pre-match to post-match dataset (Table S2). For each relevant

covariate, bias reduction was calculated as $100 \cdot (B_{pre} - B_{post}) / B_{pre}$, where B_{pre} and B_{post} are the percentage bias before and after matching, respectively. Percent bias B was calculated as: $100 \cdot (\mu_t - \mu_c) \cdot (0.5 \cdot (\sigma_t^2 + \sigma_c^2))^{-0.5}$, where μ_t and μ_c are the mean of treated and control units, and σ_t and σ_c are the standard deviation of the treated and control units. SMD

Evaluation 2b

To conduct evaluation 2b, we used RTA data, SCP-HAT consumption statistics, and country-level human population and GDP data. We employed a DID method with matching to analyse changes in footprint insourcing of countries before and after RTA, comparing them with countries that did not have an RTA. We ensured comparability between these countries in terms of GDP, baseline insourcing prior to the RTA, and the years during which the changes in footprints were assessed. Fig. 1b depicts the analytical framework, with each step described in detail below. Step 1. Create pools of treated and control units from the data. The SCP-HAT data was filtered to include information on countries' footprint insourcing. We selected cases with an RTA in place for two years as treated units, and cases without an RTA as the control group. Step 2. Find a matched control for each treated unit. To match each treated unit with a control, we identified cases from the relevant control pools that shared similar country characteristics, including GDP and the level of insourcing footprints three years prior. Nearest neighbour matching with replacement was employed by simulating various calliper width to achieve sufficient balance between the treatment and controls for all relevant covariates. Step 3. Estimate the RTA effect on the matched dataset. We fitted an OLS model to the matched dataset to estimate the effect of RTA on the change in countries' footprint insourcing (in log scale), i.e. $\log(DRF2) - \log(DRF-1) = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 TA$ (4) DRF2 represents the extent of insourcing footprint two years postRTA implementation, while DRF-1 indicates the extent of insourcing one year prior to the RTA. TA is a binary variable denoting treatment (RTA) and control (no RTA) status. A significantly positive γ_1 suggests that the RTA increases footprint insourcing, whereas a negative value indicates a decrease. Step 4. Estimate the effect of the number of RTA-connected nations. While the previous step compared the impact of RTA presence versus absence, it is noteworthy to investigate how the number of countries linked through RTA influences footprint insourcing. To investigate this, we applied an OLS model to the matched data, i.e. $\log(DRF2) - \log(DRF-1) = \delta_0 + \delta_1 NTA$ (5) DRF2 represents the extent of insourcing footprint two years postRTA implementation, while DRF-1 indicates the extent of insourcing one year before. NTA refers to the number of producing countries linked to a nation through an RTA. In addition to assessing the overall impact of RTAs, we examined the economic heterogeneity across countries. HICs and UMICs were analysed collectively, as were LMICs and LICs, to highlight the general differences between these two economic levels. to assess the quality of the matching, including examining the density distribution of the treated and control units before and after matching (Fig. S2), quantifying the standardised mean differences (SMD) between the treated and control units of the post-match data, and the bias reduction from the pre-match to post-match dataset (Table S3). The post-match datasets had SMD <0.035 and a substantial improvement over the pre-match data in the region of overlap between the treatments and controls for all controlled variables (with bias reductions of 89.5%, on average) (Table S3; Fig. S2).

The effect of RTAs' environmental provisions on footprint outsourcing

The third research objective aimed to assess hypothesis H3 or how the strength of environmental clauses in RTAs influences the extent of footprint outsourcing by countries. The key intervention is the strength of environmental provisions within RTAs. We used RTA data, RTA's strength of environmental provision dataset, SCP-HAT consumption data, country-level human population, GDP, and economic status, as well as distance between countries. Table A3 outlines the hypothesis that guides our assessment, supported by relevant sources, and accompanied by the datasets used to evaluate it. We used a DID approach with matching to compare changes in countries' footprint outsourcing before and after the implementation of RTAs with "strong" or "medium" environmental provisions, relative to countries with RTAs that include "weak," "very weak," or no environmental provisions. We ensured comparability between the countries in terms of GDP, distance, baseline outsourcing prior to RTA signing, and the years during which the changes in footprints were assessed. The analytical framework is shown in Fig. 1c, with each step explained below. Step 1. Create pools of treated and control units from the data. We began by filtering the SCP-HAT dataset to concentrate on country pairs where outsourcing take place. For the treated units, we selected pairs of trading countries that had implemented an RTA with "strong" or "medium" environmental

provisions for at least two years. For the control group, we chose pairs of trading countries that had an RTA with “weak,” “very weak,” or no environmental provisions during the same period. Step 2. Find a matched control for each treated unit. For each treated unit, we identified a matching unit from the control group that was from the same home country but had a different outsourcing partner. We ensured that the partner had comparable characteristics to the treated unit, including GDP, geographical proximity to the home country, and the extent of outsourcing three years earlier. To achieve sufficient covariate balance between the treated and control units, we applied nearest neighbour matching with replacement by simulating various calliper widths. Step 3. Estimate the RTA’s environmental provisions on the matched dataset. We applied an OLS model to the matched dataset to estimate the impact of the strength of environmental provisions in the RTA on countries’ outsourcing of their environmental footprint (in log scale), i.e. $\log(\text{IRF}_2) - \log(\text{IRF}_{-1}) = \theta_0 + \theta_1 \text{EP}$ (6) IRF₂ represents outsourcing footprints observed two years after the implementation of the RTA, while IRF₋₁ reflects outsourcing footprints one year before. EP is a binary variable that indicates the treatment group (RTAs with “strong” or “medium” environmental provisions) and the control group (RTAs with “weak,” “very weak,” or no environmental provisions). A significantly positive value of θ_1 suggests that RTAs with “strong” or “medium” environmental provisions are linked to greater outsourcing of footprints compared to those with “weak,” “very weak,” or no provisions, whereas a negative value implies lower outsourcing. Step 4. Perform robustness checks. Diagnostic tests were performed to assess the robustness of the post-match data by assessing the region of overlap between the treated and control units (Fig. S3) and quantifying the SMD and bias reduction (Table S4). The post-match datasets had SMD <0.098 and a substantial improvement over the pre-match data in the region of overlap between the treatments and controls for all controlled variables (with bias reductions of 83.5%, on average) (Table S4 and Fig. S3 for two and four years after the RTA implementation).

3.4 Results

The results are structured according to the three research questions or hypotheses we aimed to evaluate. We begin by presenting our findings on global trends in resource footprints and trade, independent of RTA, focusing on overall footprint patterns and by resource origin. Next, we describe how RTAs affect the footprints of countries, distinguishing between outsourced and insourced resources. Finally, we present how the stringency of environmental clauses in RTAs affect footprint outsourcing and their long-term effectiveness. A more detailed discussion of the implications of these findings is provided in the Discussion section.

What are the trends in natural resource use and trade globally, regardless of RTA?

The extent of a country’s natural resource footprints for primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use, both sourced domestically and externally, corresponds systematically to its level of economic growth (Fig. 3). The highest per capita footprints were found in HICs, followed by UMICs, LMICs, and LICs, respectively. Between 1990 and 2018, HIC per capita consumption of primary energy was constantly at four times the global average of 71.3 GJ person⁻¹ year⁻¹ (Fig. 3a; Table S5). While consumption by UMICs, LMICs, and LICs decreased by 1.7–1.8% each year (Table S6). In recent periods, primary energy consumption in LMICs and LICs fell sharply below the global average, with current consumption accounting for barely a-third and one-tenth of the global average, respectively. In terms of raw material consumption, HICs used three times the global average of 10.4 tonnes person⁻¹ year⁻¹ over the last three decades, whereas LMICs and LICs fell short, with current consumption per capita representing only half and a quarter of the global average, respectively (Fig. 3b; Table S5).

Per capita consumption of blue water and land use footprints decreased across all country types in the last three decades (Fig. 3c-d; Table S5). This is most likely because the world’s land and water supplies are finite, and as the population expands, the quantity of resources available per person decreases. Nonetheless, HICs’ blue water footprints remain one-and-a-half the global average of 155.6 m³ person⁻¹ year⁻¹, and land use footprints are twice as large (Table S5). Yet, the blue water footprints of LMICs and LICs are currently only half and one-fifth of the global average, respectively, while the land use footprint is equal to the global average (Table S5). The global trends thus reveal a growing disparity in natural resource use between wealthier and poorer nations.

her country types, but they also exhibit a significantly greater proportion of outsourced environmental footprints compared to those that are insourced (Fig. 4). Between 1990 and 2018, HICs outsourced 75% of their total primary energy consumption, whereas UMICs, LMICs, and LICs outsourced less than 67% (Fig. 4a). Additionally, HICs outsourced 68% of their raw materials during this period, while the other country types outsourced less than 49% (Fig. 4b). Similarly, in HICs, outsourcing accounted for 81% of blue water consumption and 72% of land use, whereas for other country types, outsourcing made up less than 65% of blue water consumption and less than 35% of land use (Fig. 4c-d).

A gravity model revealed that extent of footprint outsourcing generally increase proportionally to a country's GDP and its geographical proximity to the countries to which outsourcing occurs (Fig. 5). In terms of resource exports, countries with primary energy exports below \$1,000 are more likely to export raw materials than those with higher GDPs (Fig. 5b). Moreover, as the GDPs of countries decline, the exports of blue water and land use tend to rise (Fig. 5c-d). These findings suggest that resource flows are driven by a disparity in economic power, with higher-GDP countries predominantly importing resources from lower-GDP countries, highlighting the unequal nature of global trade in resource footprints.

Figure 3 Resource footprint by countries' economic status. Left: The change in resource footprint of countries with varying economic levels: high-income countries (HICs), upper-middle-income countries (UMICs), low-middle-income countries (LMICs), and low-income countries (LICs), in terms of (a) primary energy, (b) raw materials, (c) blue water, and (d) land use, annually between 1990 and 2018. Red lines indicate the consumption trends for each economic level (with P denoting the p-value of the trend's slope over time),

while blue lines indicate the average or fair share of the global resource uses. Right: Long-term average (1990–2018) of resource footprint of countries by economic status relative to the global fair share. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, refer to the web version of this article.)

Does RTA affect countries' outsourcing and insourcing of resources footprints?

RTAs in force by 2020 with the EU leading the way with 77 RTAs. Trade agreements have boosted international ties between nations during the last 60 years. Between 1960 and 1980, the average number of countries with which a nation had trade agreements was just 7, with Western European states having the strongest linkages to 45 other countries (Fig. 6a) spanning four continents (Fig. 6b). Between 1980 and 2000, the average number of countries with whom a country has trade agreements increased to 24, and between 2000 and 2020, it increased to 38, with EU member states having the greatest ties to over 85 countries across five continents

Following two years of the RTA's implementation, we found that, in comparison to countries without any RTA links, the scale of footprint outsourcing from signatory countries increased dramatically (Fig. 7a). Participating nations in RTAs were linked to increased outsourcing of primary energy by 12.5% (95% Confidence Interval (CI) 1.5–24.8%) compared to non-RTA countries, raw material by 18.6% (CI 6.8–31.7%), and land use footprints by 27.2% (CI 13.8–42.1%), but not in blue water footprints (Table B1 in Appendix B). These patterns were similarly observed in HICs, with the outsourcing of primary energy increased by 11.6% (CI -1.2–25.9%), raw material by 13.6% (CI 2.6–25.7%), and land use footprints by 33.5% (CI 13.8–56.5%). On the other hand, in UMICs only the raw material outsourcing increased (Table B1). The patterns of outsourcing in primary energy, raw materials, and land use among HICs were largely driven by their transfer of production to LMICs and LICs (Table B2).

nd LICs (Table B2). RTAs not only benefit consuming nations by increasing access to imported resources, but it also allows these countries to preserve their local natural resource endowments. Our findings showed that after two years of RTA participation, the consumption of locally sourced primary energy, especially for higher-income countries (HICs and UMICs), reduced by 48.3% (CI 0.1–73.6%) compared to countries without RTA involvement, and the consumption of local blue water reduced by 15.4% (CI 0.5–28.1%) (Table B3). The greater the number of countries linked to consuming countries through RTAs, the larger the reduction in consuming countries' reliance on their domestically sourced natural RTAs, higher-income countries were able to reduce insourcing of primary energy by 3.6% (CI 0.1–7.0%) and blue water by 2.3% (CI 0.8–3.8%) (Fig. 7b; Table B4). This indicates that the RTA ties allow consuming countries, especially those with strong economies, to retain their domestic resources while offshoring their footprints overseas.

Figure 4 Resource footprint by countries' economic status, total and outsourced. Resource footprint of countries in terms of (a) primary energy, (b) raw materials, (c) blue water, and (d) land use, and the volume and percent share of those imported (outsourced). Countries are broken down by economic level: high-income countries (HICs), upper-middle-income countries (UMICs), low-middle-income countries (LMICs), and low-income countries (LICs). Error bars represent the 95 % confidence intervals. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, refer to the web version of this article.)

Figure 5 . Imported resources in relation to the trade participant's socioeconomic features. The extent of imported or outsourced footprint, including (a) primary energy, (b) raw materials, (c) blue water, and (d) land use, in relation to yearly variation, the distance between consumer and producer countries involved in trade (in log scale), and the GDPs of these countries (in log scale), estimated using a gravity model. Shaded areas represent the 95% confidence interval of the curve (fitted by the Generalised Additive Models). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, refer to the web version of this article.)

Do environmental provisions in RTAs affect countries' outsourcing of environmental footprint?

Between 1980 and 2020, there were 455 RTAs signed; of these, 82.2% were deemed to have no or very weak environmental clauses, 15.2% to be weak, and 2.6% to be medium or strong. RTAs with a “weak” environmental clause first emerged in 1995, while those with “medium” and “strong” clauses first appeared in 2000 and 2009, respectively, indicating a desire to make environmental provisions more stringent in RTAs. The EU and the US are the most common signatories to RTAs with “medium” and “strong” environmental provisions.

Our analysis revealed that the strength of environmental provisions in RTAs yielded mixed outcomes across various footprint indicators. Following the adoption of RTAs for two years, the outsourcing of raw materials by countries with environmentally stricter RTAs decreased by 15.3% (CI 5.7–24.0%) in comparison to those from nations with weaker RTAs of similar characteristics. Nevertheless, the outsourcing of land use increased by 22.8% (CI 11.1–35.8%) (Fig. 7c; Table B5). The outsourcing of primary energy and blue waters is unaffected by the stringency of RTA's environmental provisions. Nonetheless, a longerterm evaluation conducted up to four years after

the implementation of the RTA shows that the effectiveness of the stricter regulations decreased over time (Fig. 7c; Table B5). This suggests that businesses may have rapidly adapted, reducing the effect of the regulatory constraints.

3.5 Discussion

Here, we discuss the implications of the findings presented in the Results section. We begin by addressing the asymmetrical nature of trade influenced by power imbalances among nations with differing economic positions. Subsequently, we discuss how RTAs amplify existing inequalities among member countries, followed by a discussion of the limited long-term effectiveness of the environmental provisions within RTAs. Finally, we outline the limitations of our analysis and suggest potential avenues for future research and improvement

Figure 6 Expansion of trade agreements. Trade agreements connecting (a) countries and (b) regions globally, and their expansion over three time periods between 1960 and 2020.

Ecologically unequal exchange under global economic inequality

The relationship between international trade, economic growth, and environmental sustainability is complex and often subject to debate. While trade is often viewed as a way to promote prosperity and sustainable development (World Bank 2018; OECD 2023), the broader socio-ecological effects are posing substantial challenges, particularly when considering the disparities in economic baselines across different nations globally (Althouse et al., 2023; Bruckner et al., 2023). Our gravity model shows that, regardless of RTA, resource imports are stronger when the importing country's GDP is higher, and the exporting country's GDP is lower. This emphasises the unbalanced nature of

trade and global value chains, and the power inequalities that exist between countries of differing economic positions (Althouse et al., 2023).

Higher income levels boost purchasing power, increasing demand for resource-intensive goods such as electronics, cars, and processed foods, which require significant energy, materials, land, and water to produce. This leads to higher per capita resource footprints in wealthier populations. Affluent nations exemplify these consumption patterns, but also tend to adopt ambitious environmental policies as public demand for environmental public goods increases (Fredriksson et al., 2005). However, maintaining high consumption levels while pursuing environmental goals presents a challenge, unless there are places outside their country's borders where resource-intensive production may be outsourced to lessen domestic impacts (Berry et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2018). Meanwhile, the legacy of colonialism and geopolitical marginalisation have left many resource-rich countries burdened with entrenching their position as suppliers of raw materials and basic manufacturing within the global economy (Hornborg and Martinez-Alier, 2016; Infante-Amate and Krausmann, 2019). Early industrialised, wealthier nations, on the other hand, benefit disproportionately by importing inexpensive raw materials from less affluent countries and goods that cause pollution during their production in those countries, while exporting high-value products (Hornborg and Martinez-Alier, 2016; Infante-Amate and Krausmann, 2019). Our result supports previous research that estimates the annual net appropriation of over 10 billion tonnes of embodied raw materials from poorer countries through a process known as ecologically unequal exchange (Dorninger et al., 2021). The impact of resource consumption in richer nations being offshored to poorer countries and the net appropriation of resources from these countries generates an annual flow of \$10 trillion. This amount represents a loss to poorer nations that is thirty times greater than the value of foreign aid they receive (Hickel et al., 2022).

RTAs amplify existing inequalities among participating countries

Our analysis further reveal that the growth of RTAs appears to be aggravating the impact of existing power imbalances among participating nation. It enables wealthier consuming countries to enhance the preservation of some of their domestic resources while offshoring their footprints abroad, a process known as environmental impact or burden shifting (Akizu-Gardoki et al., 2021; Presberger and Bernauer, 2023). Under such circumstances, certain regions or countries bear the environmental and social costs of resource extraction for the benefit of more economically powerful nations (de LT Oliveira and Hecht, 2017; Zografos and Robbins, 2020). Our findings corroborate a number of previous studies evaluating the environmental impact of RTAs, indicating that RTAs increase environmental impact shifting from wealthy to poorer nations (Jonsson et al., 2023; Kolcava et al., 2019; Presberger and Bernauer, 2023), although our analysis is based on more comprehensive data and empirical models.

The shifting environmental impact in wealthy countries, driven by the rise of RTAs, highlights a paradox for global sustainability. Outsourcing pollution and resource depletion creates a misleading sense of environmental progress, as these nations report lower domestic emissions and resource use while their consumption continues to inflict environmental damage abroad. As Requena-i-Mora and Brockington (2021) highlight, many affluent countries achieve high rankings on the Environmental Performance Index (EPI), which focuses exclusively on domestic environmental improvements, despite their substantial consumption levels and extensive material footprints derived from overseas (Fanning et al., 2022). As data enabling the tracing of resource use to its origin becomes increasingly available (Lenzen et al., 2017), it is imperative to adopt more comprehensive metrics that incorporate environmental performance both within and beyond national borders, such as Carbon Footprint and Material Footprint indices (Lenzen et al., 2022). Reliance on naïve indices in the context of a globalised world risks undermining the essence of the UN SDGs.

Figure 7 Impact of RTA and environmental provision on countries' footprint outsourcing and insourcing. (a) The effect of RTA participation on countries' footprint outsourcing, (b) the effect of the number of countries linked via RTAs on footprint insourcing, and (c) the effect of environmental provisions' stringency in RTAs on countries' footprint outsourcing through time. For (c), the effect was estimated as the difference in the change of countries' footprint outsourcing (in log scale) under 'medium' or 'strong' RTAs compared to those under 'weak', 'very weak', or no environmental provision within one to four years of RTA implementation. The assessment of primary energy was limited to three years of RTA implementation due to insufficient matched data for estimation. Error bars represent the 95% confidence intervals. The notation below each bar indicates the significance level: *** p-value < 0.001, ** p-value < 0.01, * p-value < 0.05, + p-value < 0.1, and ns for non-significance

RTAs' environmental provisions have limited long-term effectiveness

dress the repercussions of increasing trade. While our analysis did find that stricter environmental provisions serve as a short-term remedy for the import of certain resources, such as raw materials, they have not proven effective beyond two years of the adoption. We found that stricter environmental provisions had negligible or worsening effects on imported footprints for primary energy, blue water, and land use, regardless of the timeframe. Our findings contradict previous

research, which found environmental provisions to be effective (Abman et al., 2024; Berger et al., 2020; Brandi et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2017). However, it is noteworthy that most of these studies assessed commodity imports or environmental outcomes only within the first or second year following the implementation of environmental provisions. A recent study by Presberger and Bernauer (2023), who used a similar dataset to ours but employed a different methodological approach and examined outcomes one-year post-RTA implementation, also found that resource outsourcing reduced with environmental provision, albeit marginally.

Our findings on the limited long-term impact of RTAs' environmental provisions may be attributed to several factors. Recent studies have determined that the majority of RTAs incorporating stricter environmental provisions do not significantly surpass weaker RTAs or those lacking such provisions, and these provisions often remain ambiguous in terms of sustainability obligations (Hradilova and Svoboda, 2018; Morin and Jinnah, 2018). Beyond the specific clauses within RTAs, studies examining individual cases in greater detail have highlighted critical limitations. While some mandatory standards have been established, these agreements often lack robust legal frameworks to enforce environmental protections and include insufficient dispute resolution mechanisms to ensure compliance with sustainability standards (Baccini, 2019; Friel et al., 2020; Heyl et al., 2021; Martínez-Zarzoso et al., 2023). Furthermore, under conditions of consistently high or increasing demand for commodities, businesses may prioritise capitalising on market opportunities. Consequently, there are strong incentives to disregard or deliberately circumvent regulations to expedite production processes (Carvalho et al., 2019; Lyon and Maxwell, 2019). This dynamic may lead to a gradual decline in the efficacy of environmental provisions over time.

Study caveats and future research

Future research. We did not examine the environmental impact of individual sectors. Certain sectors, such as energy and agriculture, may have significantly higher resource consumption compared to others, even within the same trade region (Johnson et al., 2021; Mantoam et al., 2020). Gaining sector-specific insights could help design targeted interventions, such as promoting sustainable production practices or reducing emissions in high-impact industries. Evaluating the effects of specific trade agreements could also highlight opportunities for more effective bilateral or multilateral cooperation. A more detailed analysis of the environmental provisions in RTAs would also help us better understand how certain policies either support or hinder the mitigation of environmental impact shifting. Such insights could help countries within RTAs work together more meaningfully to tackle shared environmental challenges and promote collective accountability for environmental degradation (Bowen et al., 2017; Muradian et al., 2025)

Additionally, we did not examine the differences between North-South and South-South trade agreements. Lechner and Spilker (2022) observed that environmental clauses within South-South trade agreements are increasingly common and, contrary to earlier assumptions, demonstrate greater efficacy in reducing air pollution emissions among participating nations than those in North-South agreements. Several previous research reported similar findings (Brandi et al., 2019; Zhou et al., 2017). This enhanced effectiveness may stem from a shared recognition among southern nations of the concrete societal impacts associated with climate and environmental change, contrasting with the more abstract perceptions common in northern countries (Hase et al., 2021; McAllister et al., 2024; Olausson and Berglez, 2014).

Furthermore, our analysis of flows between nations and regions shows inequalities between countries with different economic statuses but does not address the unequal distribution of consumption among different socioeconomic groups within nations. Despite increases in per capita incomes and the associated consumption emissions over the last decades, which have helped to create a global middle class and allowed millions to escape poverty in developing countries, the world's richest households in wealthier nations have continued to emit more (Chancel, 2022; Nielsen et al., 2024). Nearly half the growth observed has merely allowed the already wealthy top 10% to augment their consumption and enlarge their carbon footprints, with all the damage this entails. Historical and ongoing inequality will pass down to future generations, unless more efforts are made to reduce the continued outsized impact of the minority group of the world's wealthiest individuals, wherever they reside, as well as addressing the continuing development needs and aspirations of the world's poorest citizens (Kartha et al., 2020).

3.6 Conclusion

The evidence presented in this article reinforces other sources that demonstrate the stark inequalities in international trade, involving significant flows of resource from poorer to wealthier nations and the outsourcing of negative environmental impacts. By employing more rigorous data and analytical methods, we provide new evidence that this outsourcing of environmental impacts is intensifying, with increasing RTAs driving higher resource transfers in recent decades. While stricter environmental provisions in RTAs have been introduced as a short-term measure, they have proven neither sufficient nor sustainable. The growing demands of affluent nations further challenge the long-term effectiveness of such measures. Concurrently, poorer nations, which serve as the primary suppliers of global resources, are increasingly burdened by climate change, exacerbating their vulnerability to the cycle of resource exploitation and socio-ecological harm. Broader evidence indicates that environmental degradation and climate change pose increasing barriers to economic growth, while there is insufficient evidence supporting the feasibility of green growth decoupling at the scale, speed, and permanence required (Hickel and Kallis, 2020; InfanteAmate et al., 2024). This underscores the urgent need for deliberate shifts to tackle overconsumption, rising inequality, and ecological harm.

Affluent nations need to reduce their material consumption to mitigate the socio-ecological impacts of resource extraction in less affluent countries. Engaging in open dialogue about imposing absolute limits on consumption, guided by the principles of material sufficiency, may offer a constructive path forward. As highlighted by Dunlop and Volker (2023), achieving sustainability requires a clearer understanding of what defines “needs” and “enough” in the context of consumption, enabling us to reshape material supply and consumption systems accordingly. Achieving meaningful sustainability transformations will demand not only the adoption of degrowth strategies but also comprehensive structural reforms to the global financial architecture (Dempsey et al., 2024; Ghosh et al., 2025). In parallel, integrating environmental footprint data into assessments of a country’s environmental performance is essential for mitigating biases that disproportionately benefit high-consumption nations that rely on outsourcing production. As such data becomes more accessible, these metrics can better align national environmental performance with the UN SDGs, particularly Goal 12 (responsible consumption and production). Reforming RTAs to incorporate ecological footprint accountability and establish resource-equity mechanisms, such as ecological premiums on resource-intensive imports, represents a critical step toward sustainable global practices. Finally, whilst our analysis shows that RTAs and current environmental measures often have negative or limited effects, this should not be seen as an argument for isolationism or protectionism. Instead, we advocate for critically rethinking trade frameworks through the lens of ecological limits and distributive justice, ensuring that economic integration supports, rather than undermines, environmental sustainability and global equity.

Twitter Counterfactual analysis over 3 decades shows that trade deals intensified environmental impact shifting. While stricter environmental clauses briefly curbed some footprints, effects were short-lived.

CRedit authorship contribution statement Truly Santika: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. Valerie Nelson: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. Jeremy Haggard: Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition. Indika Thushari: Writing – review & editing, Investigation

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Appendix A

The tables below provide a summary of the analyses carried out in this study, the hypotheses or underlying rationale guiding the investigation, supported by pertinent references, and the datasets employed to evaluate these hypotheses.

Table A1

Analysis 1: Trends in resource footprints and trade globally, regardless of RTA.

<i>Analysis objective</i>	<i>Hypothesis or rationale underpinning the investigation, supported by relevant references</i>	<i>Datasets used to assess the hypothesis and their sources</i>
Evaluation (1a). Assess the patterns of resource consumption across countries, irrespective of resource origin.	The per capita environmental footprints of nations are typically positively correlated with their level of economic development (Wiedmann et al., 2015; Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020).	Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country’s economic status (high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low income). Source: The World Bank (2024)
Evaluation (1b). Assess the patterns of resource consumption across countries by resource origin (insourced vs. outsourced).	As nations experience economic growth, they often decrease the share of material extraction conducted domestically by relying more on imported (outsourced) resources (Wiedmann et al., 2015).	Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country’s economic status (high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low income). Source: The World Bank (2024)
Evaluation (1c). Assess the patterns of resource outsourcing across countries in relation to the socio-economic features of the trade participants.	Imported (outsourced) footprint generally increase proportionally with a country’s GDP and its geographical proximity to outsourced countries (Bruckner et al., 2023; Chaney, 2018; Wiedmann et al., 2015). Less affluent countries are more dependent on resource exports or basic manufacturing.	Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country’s GDP per capita. Source: The World Bank (2024) Distance between countries, measured as the distance between their respective capital cities. Source: World Cities database.

Table A2

Analysis 2: RTA's effect on countries' footprints, whether outsourced or insourced.

Analysis objective	Hypothesis or rationale underpinning the investigation, supported by relevant references	Datasets used to assess the hypothesis and their sources
Evaluation (2a). Assess the impact of RTA on countries' footprint outsourcing.	RTAs can elevate the outsourcing footprints of countries (Jönsson et al., 2023; Kolcava et al., 2019; Presberger and Bernauer, 2023). The extent of footprint outsourcing by a country in a particular year can be influenced by various factors, including the GDPs of both the home and outsourcing nations (Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020), the geographical distance between these countries (Chaney, 2018), and the timing (year) of trade influenced by global events (e.g., wars) (Zhu et al., 2024). These factors must be accounted for when evaluating the impact of RTAs on footprint outsourcing.	RTA data. Source: Trade Agreements Database (World Trade Organization, 2024) Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country's GDP per capita. Source: The World Bank (2024) Country's economic status (high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low income). Source: The World Bank (2024) Distance between countries, measured as the distance between their respective capital cities. Source: World Cities database. RTA data. Source: Trade Agreements Database (World Trade Organization, 2024)
Evaluation (2b). Assess the impact of RTA on countries' footprint insourcing.	RTAs can result in the shifting of environmental impacts, where a portion of the overall footprint is transferred to other countries, while simultaneously decreasing the domestic footprint (Jönsson et al., 2023; Kolcava et al., 2019; Presberger and Bernauer, 2023). The extent of domestic footprint (insourcing) by a country in a particular year can be influenced by various factors, including the country's GDP (Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020) and the specific timing (year), which may be influenced by global events (Zhu et al., 2024). These factors must be controlled when evaluating the impact of RTAs on footprint insourcing.	Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country's GDP per capita. Source: The World Bank (2024) Country's economic status (high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low income). Source: The World Bank (2024)

Table A3

Analysis 3: Environmental provision's effect on countries' footprint outsourcing.

Analysis objective	Hypothesis or rationale underpinning the investigation, supported by relevant references	Datasets used to assess the hypothesis and their sources
Assess the impact of stringent environmental clauses in RTAs on the outsourcing of footprint.	Environmental provisions in RTAs have the potential to minimise footprint outsourcing of countries (Abman et al., 2024; Brandi et al., 2020). The extent of footprint outsourcing by a country in a particular year can be influenced by various factors, including the GDPs of both the home and outsourcing nations (Zambrano-Monserrate et al., 2020), the geographical distance between these countries (Chaney, 2018), and the timing (year) of trade influenced by global events (e.g., wars) (Zhu et al., 2024). These factors must be accounted for when evaluating the impact of RTA's environmental provision on footprint outsourcing.	RTA data. Source: Trade Agreements Database (World Trade Organization, 2024) RTA's strength of environmental provisions. Source: Santika et al. (2024) Footprints of countries globally. Source: SCP-HAT (Sustainable Consumption and Production Hotspot Analysis Tool) database (UN Environment, 2024) Total human population in each nation. Source: UN Population Division (2023) Country's GDP per capita. Source: The World Bank (2024) Country's economic status (high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low income). Source: The World Bank (2024) Distance between countries, measured as the distance between their respective capital cities. Source: World Cities database.

Appendix B

Table B1

The estimated effect of RTA participation on countries' footprint outsourcing from 1990 to 2018, overall and broken down by countries' economic level: high-income countries (HICs), upper-middle-income countries (UMICs), and low-middle-income and low-income countries (LMICs and LICs). Resource footprints evaluated include primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use.

Footprint indicator	Countries' economic level	Estimated effect of RTA participation (parameter β_1 in Eq. (3), with 95% CI and p-value \ast)		
Overall				
Primary energy		12.54%	(1.51%, 24.76%)	●●
Raw material		18.63%	(6.84%, 31.72%)	●●●
Blue water		-1.71%	(-6.05%, 2.84%)	
Land use		27.17%	(13.81%, 42.10%)	●●●●
By countries' economic level				
Primary energy	HICs	11.57%	(-1.17%, 25.95%)	+
	UMICs	19.93%	(-5.59%, 52.36%)	
	LMICs and LICs	7.81%	(-14.51%, 35.97%)	
Raw material	HICs	13.55%	(2.55%, 25.72%)	●
	UMICs	38.06%	(3.16%, 84.76%)	●

(continued on next page)

Table B1 (continued)

Footprint indicator	Countries' economic level	Estimated effect of RTA participation (parameter β_1 in Eq. (3), with 95% CI and p-value ‡)	
Blue water	LMICs and LICs	16.59%	(-16.37%, 62.56%)
	HICs	1.93%	(-5.37%, 9.80%)
	UMICs	-7.61%	(-16.18%, 1.85%)
Land use	LMICs and LICs	-2.98%	(-9.25%, 3.71%)
	HICs	33.50%	(13.84%, 56.55%)
	UMICs	2.80%	(-17.78%, 28.53%)
	LMICs and LICs	12.85%	(-7.77%, 38.09%)

‡ ●●● p-value < 0.001, ●● p-value < 0.01, ● p-value < 0.05, + p-value < 0.1.

Table B2

The estimated effect of RTA participation on countries' outsourcing of resource footprints from 1990 to 2018, categorised by the economic status of home and outsourced country pairs (with 95% CI and p-value ‡). The assessed resource footprints include: (a) primary energy, (b) raw materials, (c) blue water, and (d) land use. A positive value indicates increased outsourcing. Bolded figures denote statistically significant effects.

(a) Primary energy	Outsourced countries		
Home countries	HICs	UMICs	LMICs/LICs
HICs	16.72%	-8.09%	18.61%
	(-43.62%, 141.65%) ns	(-28.49%, 18.10%) ns	(3.50%, 35.95%) ●●
	n = 30	n = 68	n = 204
UMICs	75.17%	-34.53%	49.45%
	(-7.82%, 232.56%) +	(-62.34%, 13.81%) ns	(16.09%, 92.38%) ●●
	n = 14	n = 46	n = 58
LMICs/LICs	14.69%	-21.57%	19.47%
	(-22.74%, 70.25%) ns	(-42.37%, 6.76%) ns	(-31.06%, 107.03%) ns
	n = 16	n = 60	n = 44
(b) Raw materials	Outsourced countries		
Home countries	HICs	UMICs	LMICs/LICs
HICs	35.59%	16.92%	17.83%
	(-20.36%, 127.46%) ns	(-0.75%, 37.71%) +	(3.75%, 33.83%) ●●
	n = 22	n = 92	n = 236
UMICs	84.14%	56.72%	2.21%
	(-4.62%, 250.48%) +	(2.51%, 139.62%) ●	(-31.57%, 52.68%) ns
	n = 38	n = 28	n = 46
LMICs/LICs	81.21%	-25.31%	19.34%
	(-25.41%, 340.21%) ns	(-54.25%, 21.93%) ns	(-20.31%, 78.71%) ns
	n = 30	n = 32	n = 44
(c) Blue water	Outsourced countries		
Home countries	HICs	UMICs	LMICs/LICs
HICs	-0.07%	-2.65%	4.71%
	(-5.66%, 5.86%) ns	(-10.75%, 6.17%) ns	(-6.51%, 17.27%)
	n = 40	n = 128	n = 270
UMICs	-18.32%	-3.99%	-1.38%
	(-30.95%, -3.40%) ●	(-12.86%, 5.76%) ns	(-22.76%, 25.91%)
	n = 58	n = 68	n = 56
LMICs/LICs	0.81%	-13.58%	1.65%
	(-3.63%, 5.46%) ns	(-31.55%, 9.10%) ns	(-11.57%, 16.86%)
	n = 180	n = 78	n = 92
(d) Land use	Outsourced countries		
Home countries	HICs	UMICs	LMICs/LICs
HICs	-20.33%	-16.13%	65.60%
	(-45.68%, 18.85%) ns	(-32.57%, 0.15%) +	(33.11%, 106.02%) ●●●
	n = 28	n = 108	n = 280
UMICs	1.72%	-32.03%	38.35%
	(-30.84%, 49.62%) +	(-54.08%, 0.68%) +	(-5.09%, 101.67%) +
	n = 40	n = 50	n = 70
LMICs/LICs	47.35%	-9.47%	8.83%
	(-1.41%, 120.25%) +	(-36.52%, 29.08%) ns	(-17.47%, 43.50%) ns
	n = 28	n = 34	n = 28

‡ ●●● p-value < 0.001, ●● p-value < 0.01, ● p-value < 0.05, + p-value < 0.1.

Table B3

The estimated effect of RTA participation on countries' footprint insourcing two years after the RTA implementation. Analyses were based on data between 1990 and 2018, and include primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use.

Footprint indicator	Countries' economic level	Estimated effect of RTA participation (parameter γ_1 in Eq. (4), with 95% CI and p-value ‡)	
Overall			
Primary energy		-29.86%	(-47.41%, -6.46%) ●
Raw material		-18.56%	(-34.31%, 0.96%) +

Table B3 (continued)

Footprint indicator	Countries' economic level	Estimated effect of RTA participation (parameter γ_1 in Eq. (4), with 95 % CI and p-value ‡)		
Blue water		4.58%	(-15.48%, 29.41%)	
Land use		4.48%	(-10.13%, 21.46%)	
By countries' economic level				
Primary energy	HICs and UMICs	-48.35%	(-73.58%, -0.06%)	●
	LMICs and LICs	-17.13%	(-35.68%, 6.78%)	
Raw material	HICs and UMICs	-15.23%	(-41.05%, 21.89%)	
	LMICs and LICs	-21.13%	(-38.85%, 1.71%)	+
Blue water	HICs and UMICs	-15.42%	(-28.10%, -0.51%)	●
	LMICs and LICs	16.30%	(-14.84%, 58.82%)	
Land use	HICs and UMICs	-1.93%	(-22.47%, 24.06%)	
	LMICs and LICs	8.69%	(-11.73%, 33.84%)	

‡ ●●● p-value < 0.001, ●● p-value < 0.01, ● p-value < 0.05, + p-value < 0.1.

Table B4

The estimated effect of the number of countries linked through RTA on footprint insourcing two years after the RTA implementation. Analyses were based on data between 1990 and 2018, and include primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use.

Footprint indicator	Countries' economic level	Estimated effect of the number of nations linked by RTAs (parameter δ_1 in Eq. (5), with 95 % CI and p-value ‡)		
Overall				
Primary energy		-2.87%	(-4.71%, -0.99%)	●●
Raw material		-1.06%	(-2.76%, 0.67%)	
Blue water		-1.47%	(-2.92%, -0.01%)	●
Land use		-0.47%	(-2.69%, 2.82%)	
By countries' economic level				
Primary energy	HICs and UMICs	-3.60%	(-7.01%, -0.06%)	●
	LMICs and LICs	-1.29%	(-3.44%, 0.89%)	
Raw material	HICs and UMICs	-2.90%	(-6.27%, 0.59%)	+
	LMICs and LICs	-0.52%	(-2.35%, 1.34%)	
Blue water	HICs and UMICs	-2.31%	(-3.80%, -0.80%)	●●
	LMICs and LICs	-1.15%	(-3.15%, 0.90%)	
Land use	HICs and UMICs	0.27%	(-1.08%, 1.64%)	
	LMICs and LICs	-0.86%	(-4.40%, 2.82%)	

‡ ●●● p-value < 0.001, ●● p-value < 0.01, ● p-value < 0.05, + p-value < 0.1.

Table B5

The estimated effect of the strength of environmental provisions in RTAs on countries footprint outsourcing between 1990 and 2018, after one to four years of RTA implementation. Resource footprint evaluated include primary energy, raw materials, blue water, and land use. Shading for primary energy means that there was a limited matched dataset to estimate the impact of RTAs' environmental provisions.

Footprint indicator	Years after RTA implementation	Estimated effect of RTAs' strength of environmental provisions (parameter θ_1 in Eq. (6), with 95 % CI and p-value ‡)		
Primary energy	One year	-11.07%	(-23.84%, 3.85%)	
	Two years	5.98%	(-8.35%, 22.55%)	
	Three years	73.62%	(11.38%, 170.62%)	●
	Four years			
Raw material	One year	-22.13%	(-29.54%, -13.95%)	●●●
	Two years	-15.33%	(-24.00%, -5.66%)	●●
	Three years	-0.04%	(-13.22%, 15.14%)	
	Four years	22.81%	(-20.30%, 89.23%)	
Blue water	One year	6.05%	(-0.50%, 13.04%)	+
	Two years	1.46%	(-5.64%, 9.10%)	
	Three years	5.16%	(-7.89%, 20.04%)	
	Four years	23.96%	(2.39%, 50.08%)	●
Land use	One year	14.61%	(5.92%, 24.01%)	●●●
	Two years	22.80%	(11.09%, 35.76%)	●●●
	Three years	32.07%	(15.65%, 50.82%)	●●●
	Four years	44.20%	(24.23%, 67.38%)	●●●

‡ ●●● p-value < 0.001, ●● p-value < 0.01, ● p-value < 0.05, + p-value < 0.1.

Appendix C. Supplementary data Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2025.103028>

Data availability All data utilised in this study have been previously published. The sources of these datasets are provided in Appendix A of the manuscript.

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4. Paper 3: Achieving sustainability transformations for multi-species justice: assessing the potential of diverse legal pathways and societal struggles.

Banwell, S., Nelson, V., & Dehbi, F. (2025). Achieving sustainability transformations for multi-species justice: assessing the potential of diverse legal pathways and societal struggles. *Sustainability Science*, 20(3), 1017-1035.

Abstract This article explores the transformative potential of legal pathways and societal struggles to conserve biodiversity and achieve sustainability transformations toward multi-species justice. Exploring contemporary discourse on sustainability transformations, including emerging attention to relationality and critical perspectives, we analyse a range of legal instruments and measures to assess their transformative potential drawing upon their capacity to overcome rigid Cartesian dichotomies between humans and nature, to challenge capitalist accumulation imperatives and hence to contribute to a new societal sustainability goal of pluriversal, multi-species justice. Ranging from mainstream approaches in existing biodiversity and environmental instruments and supply chain instruments, such as environmental and deforestation due diligence, to newly emerging, more radical propositions of Rights of Nature, Ecocide and Restorative Justice, we review existing literature and empirical cases to interrogate and reflect upon their transformative potential, and to identify potentially effective combinations of socio-legal pathways.

Keywords Transformative multi-species justice · Biodiversity · Sustainability · Rights of nature · Ecocide · Restorative justice

4.1 Introduction

Socio-ecological damage is intensifying with planetary boundaries being exceeded, undermining a safe operating space for humanity (Steffen et al. 2015). This perilous situation is leading to growing academic and policy calls for sustainability transformations. Defining and achieving these remains challenging and, in this context, the role of legal pathways for achieving biodiversity conservation and sustainability transformations have not been fully explored.

The two research questions we seek to answer are as follows:

- To what extent and in what ways can legal pathways, instruments and mechanisms contribute to sustainability transformations? ·
- Which legal pathways have the most transformative potential for achieving multi-species justice?

We explore contemporary discourse on sustainability transformations, including emerging attention to relationality and critical perspectives for tackling socio-ecological damage, analysing a range of legal instruments and measures, ranging from mainstream approaches to newly emergent more radical propositions, interrogating their transformative potential.

4.2 Theoretical framework: sustainability transformations and multi-species justice

Transformative change theory

Policy discourse on sustainability frequently envisions change as part of sector or market transformations, or fixes which omit critical and relational analysis (Meadows 1999). IPBES (2022) focuses on policy levers including legal and regulatory policy instruments, analysed according to their potential to shift economic paradigms and values of nature, differentiating those that promote the status quo (e.g. Environmental Impact Assessment, commodity chain regulation) or have incremental potential (e.g. legally protected areas, locally managed marine areas). The only transformative option is Rights of Nature (RoN).

In academia, socio-ecological systems or socio-technical systems (or dynamic systems) thinking dominates transformative change theory; the former frames change through interplays of niche innovations and regimes (Fisher and Brondizio 2022). Leverage points in dynamic systems theory are strategic interventions catalysing change across systems (Meadows 1999). Mobilizing changes in values, goals and paradigms (IPBES 2022) are challenging to achieve deeper leverage points,

which reach beyond specific policies or resources (Abson et al. 2017). Leverage points thinking risks being reductive, employing mechanistic notions of reality. It can strategically refocus attention on values shifts, thereby, challenging singularized technical and accumulation-oriented solutions, in support of novel futures imaginaries, i.e. individual and collective identities of self and relations to others and place, which shape social orders (Castoriadis 1987; Taylor 2004). Another strand of transformative change theory envisions empowerment processes for marginal groups, involving democratic struggle, systemic and structural change (Scoones et al. 2020).

The relevance of relationality and More-Than-Human (MTH) thinking to sustainability has only recently emerged (West et al. 2020). Relationality understands the world as in constant flux, involving embodied, unfolding relations in complex assemblages, challenging the notion of a uniform world that can be observed by an external scientist. MTH thinking recognizes the agency, labour, sentience and value of non-humans in such assemblage processes. Shifting beyond anthropocentrism, some relational approaches embrace pluriversality, i.e. making space for plural ontologies (Feola et al. 2021). Critical perspectives on transformation address issues of power dynamics and interests, such as how capitalism causes socio-ecological damage. Capitalism controls not just economic structures, but invisibly shapes mental frameworks, influencing how people see the world and the possibilities within it. This prevents the development of alternative imaginaries (Fisher 2009). Commodifying nature, framing it as a resource, “subordinates the harms done to nature in favour of economic gain” (Doyle 2011, p. 21), what we might call a form of ecological imperialism with the potential to destroy ecosystems and biospheres (Crook and Short 2014). Active deconstruction of capitalist relations, plus practical efforts to co-create post-capitalist realities are needed (Feola et al. 2021). The wealth accumulation inherent within capitalism is premised upon humancentred utility maximisation, which ultimately and increasingly is undermining the complex webs of life (Moore 2015). As Büscher (2022) argues, there are differentiated accountabilities along socioeconomic strata for the destruction being wrought upon such webs of life, and which is further marginalizing large shares of human populations, who are treated as ‘less than human’. Capitalist dominations, in Büscher’s critique of MTH research, diminish non-humans but also certain groups of humans. Therefore, the response should not just be non-anthropocentric, by decentring humans and their concerns, but should also clearly distinguish between human concerns and perspectives, as well as amplifying non-human experiences and agencies. More radical futures, challenging accumulation imperatives, and colonial modernities and patriarchies, are commonly deemed preposterous, but are needed for sustainability transformations.

A focus on specific levers can risk reproducing dominant expert-led depoliticized techno-science solutions (Lahsen and Turnhout 2021). We argue that reflexive interrogation of the broad designs of pathways, with attention to values, paradigms and ontologies, can be productive for insights on their potential and on design improvements. Drawing upon empirical cases, we can also see the messy, everyday nuances involved in efforts to achieve sustainability transformations (Feola et al. 2021). We explore the potential of legal pathways for sustainability transformations, given that evidence is necessarily limited (IPBES 2022). We evaluate which legal pathways have the capacity to shift economic paradigms (IPBES 2022) but also go beyond IPBES and its imperative to recognize other values of nature (IPBES 2022), to ask whether leverage points and levers challenge rigid Cartesian dichotomies. Also, we recognize that transformations cannot be achieved solely by policy levers, but in general require emancipatory social movements, cosmopolitics and relationality and deliberative democracy, for example, or might require changes beyond the latter, towards potentially eco-anarchism, because of the entanglement of nation states in capitalism (Smessaert and Feola 2023). In other words, legal systems are part of wider capitalist, patriarchal and colonial modernity superstructures and formations (Arora and Stirling 2023; Plumwood 1993).

Two key questions to interrogate pathways and levers are as follows: (i) To what extent does the initiative in question overcome rigid Cartesian dichotomies (human/nature, mind/ body, subject/object) and thereby move beyond anthropocentrism? and (ii) To what extent does the lever or initiative challenge capitalist accumulation and colonial modernity imperatives, offering and co-developing alternative imaginaries, structures and practices in emancipatory processes? Further research should explore empirical cases and involve participatory action research to advance understanding (see Escobar 2018; de Sousa Santos 2014; Mignolo and Walsh 2018; Barcelos 2019; Maldonado-Torres 2017).

Multi-species justice—a transformative goal?

'Multi-species' justice or 'interspecies' ethics are based upon "care for non-humans and ecological repair that is inclusive of more-than-human-worlds" (Biswas Mellamphy and Vangeest 2024, p. 8). Rather than thinking about how humans are connected to nature, it is important to understand that we are already always involved in some way or another alongside "objects, other animals, living beings, organisms, physical forces, spiritual entities" (de La Bellacasa 2017, p. 1). Further, humans are not the only living forms to undertake care work, which circulates in the natural world, in living webs of care (de La Bellacasa 2017). Ethics of care means recognising multi-species justice and accountabilities of (certain) humans for damage, moving beyond anthropocentric notions of justice (often based on notions of the white, heterosexual, male) towards a more inclusive blueprint of justice that treats all living beings as worthy of protection and respect (Winter 2022). Plural forms of knowledge and lifeways, such as Indigenous ones, have been obscured by Western centrism (Thaler 2022), which is grounded in human exceptionalism: the distinctiveness of humans and their separation from and superiority over other species and nonhuman nature (Srinivasan and Kasturirangan 2016, as cited in Celermajer et al. 2022 p. 120). The very notion of justice is expanded by multi-species concerns (Celermajer et al. 2022, p. 127).

Anthropocentrism prioritises human superiority over other species (Raymond et al. 2023), amplifying patriarchies through controlling, objectifying and exploitative relations pertaining to women and nature (Plumwood 1993). Bio-/eco-centric worldviews appreciate the value of nature for its intrinsic worth (IPBES 2022). To elaborate, ecocentrism "...is a worldview that recognizes intrinsic value in ecosystems and the biological and physical elements that they comprise, as well as in the ecological processes that spatially and temporally connect them" (Gray et al. 2018, p. 130). The interests of humans are considered secondary to those of ecosystems and the Earth. Biocentric approaches can go some way to responding to the failures of humanism, but risk reproducing rigid Cartesian separations of humans from nature (West et al. 2020). Many biocentric counter narratives do not go far enough because "humans remain the arbiter of value" (Biswas Mellamphy and Vangeest 2024, p. 6). Relational philosophies, common among Indigenous Peoples, some Eastern religions, and in some scholarship, do not involve such dualisms (Moore 2017). Giving space for these suppressed ontologies (Quijano 2000; Mignolo and Walsh 2018) is central to pluriversal politics (Escobar 2018). Achieving change requires, at minimum, a cosmopolitics that recognizes the diversity of human and non-human actors and processes (Stengers 2010). Or going further, a pluriversal politics, i.e. struggles for plural ontologies or 'world of many worlds', drawing upon Indigenous knowledges, promoting conviviality (i.e. collectively and autonomously living well together) (Illich 1973) based on care ethics (de La Bellacasa 2017). Recognizing the agency, labour and value of nature, can be complemented by beliefs in which nature is kin (Rose 1992) with spiritual and sacred import, giving more reason to care about such diverse entanglements (de La Bellacasa 2017).

4.3 Methodological considerations

In the next section, we describe a range of legal pathways for biodiversity and sustainability, clustering these according to the extent to which they are (i) widely established in law and focus on biodiversity and environment, (ii) more recently established in certain jurisdictions and often lacking legal definition. We then analyse their transformative potential according to (a) the extent to which they address Cartesian dichotomies, particularly human–nature separations, and shift beyond anthropocentric and/or biocentric approaches, (b) the extent to which the lever can challenge capitalist and colonial modernity relations, taking into consideration both questions of design, but also implementation (see Table 1). The conceptual framing draws upon relevant literatures focusing upon transformative change, relationality, anthropocentrism, and ethics of care, to distil the two key criteria for reflexive learning on legal levers. The subsequent analyses are based upon an extensive exploration of the legal literature on biodiversity and environment, including identifying relevant studies on widely established legal mechanisms and instruments and more recent ones, as well as studies from sociology, development, green criminology and environmental fields of research, including empirical cases, which reflect upon the potential and limitations of these pathways. We also briefly explore measures which address accumulation imperatives, including at global macro-economic scales, to explore the possible necessity of mobilising these to create conditions for expanded placebased sustainability transformations.

Insights from relationality, MTH thinking and associated normative goals of ethics of care and multi-species justice can form the basis for reflexive analysis of legal and constitutional pathways for sustainability transformations. See Table 1 for broad guiding questions to explore the transformative potential of legal pathways and explore implementation challenges through several empirical cases. Rather than thinking about levers as tools for change, we are exploring deep leverage points through these guiding questions, e.g. shifts in values and onto-epistemologies, providing critical and relational analysis.

Table 1 A conceptual framework for reflexivity on potential levers for sustainability transformations (Nelson, submitted)

Assessing levers or initiatives for sustainability	Status quo	Less transformative/potential (blocking)	More transformative potential
To what extent does it overcome rigid Cartesian dichotomies and create space for care-oriented imaginaries recognizing entanglements, non-human agency and nature as kin (Onto-epistemological shifts)	Anthropocentric Prioritises human-oriented perspectives with a rigid dichotomy between humans and nature. Does not recognize nature as kin	Biocentric Prioritizes bio- or eco-centric perspectives, retaining the rigid dichotomy between humans and nature. Does not generally recognize nature as kin, i.e. having agency and labour	Pluriversal Recognizes interdependencies and entanglements between humans and nature, possibly including nature as kin, i.e. having agency and labour. Amplifies relational ontologies
To what extent do they directly or indirectly challenge accumulation and promote autonomous regeneration via pluriversal post-growth?	Status quo capitalist No constraints on consumption, no shifts in economic visions and structures	Reformist approach Seeks to modify or reform corporate practice to increase sustainability, treats market economy and growth as common sense, risks obscuring alternatives and does not tackle wider macro-economy and consumption governance	Convivial, diverse economies Promotes reciprocity focused, post-growth economies, tackles accumulation imperative and growth orientation, with a multi-species justice goal

4.4 Legal pathways for transformative change for biodiversity and sustainability

Biodiversity and human rights and environmental due diligence

International law to protect the environment began to develop in the late nineteenth century and early twentieth century through the conclusion of bilateral agreements and disputes concerned with the protection of wildlife (United Nations 2007), or protection against specific issues such as pollution (United Nations 2006). As such efforts continued to develop, they began to take on a multilateral character following the creation of the United Nations (Sands et al 2018, pp. 26–29).¹ More inclusive approaches on protection, conservation and sustainable use of the environment through the concept of biodiversity were adopted in the 1980s, allowing for the recognition of the reciprocal relationships between species and ecosystems, rather than specific species in isolation (Sands et al. 2018, p. 384). Most notable is the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (United Nations 1992) which takes a more holistic approach to the conservation and restoration of biodiversity, addressing both direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss, while mainstreaming biodiversity consideration across relevant policy areas (Sands et al. 2018, p. 387; United Nations 1992, art. 6). Initiatives adopted in response to and under the CBD are underpinned by the anthropocentric premise of nature as a vital resource for human life rather than the ecocentric premise of nature possessing value in and of itself (Taylor et al. 2020, pp. 1091–1092), and still less a relational and MTH understanding.

Legal actions focused upon biodiversity conservation, can have negative impacts on humans; while they begin to counter legal anthropocentrism by giving more attention to the environment, they continue to rigidly separate humans from nature in legal philosophy, enabling dispossessions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities. This is despite the relationality and ethics of care commonly underpinning many Indigenous philosophies and the effectiveness of Indigenous governance for territorial biodiversity. In the Indian case of T.N. Godavarman Thirumulkpad vs Union of India and Ors (1997), on the protection of Red Sanders trees from illegal logging, the court acknowledged how international treaties (CITES, CBD) and India's constitution embed an eco-

centric approach (Supreme Court of India 1997, para. 18, 20, 26; Kodiveri 2023, pp. 191, 198, 200). This led to the establishment of a quasi-judicial committee to oversee executive decision making on deforestation. As a result, forest-dwelling communities were evicted (Kodiveri 2023, pp. 188, 195), demonstrating the negative effects when legal philosophies sustain Cartesian dichotomies, and view the environment through either an anthropocentric or biocentric lens. Pragmatically, the impact of biodiversity-oriented laws on human rights should be considered in current legal actions seeking the protection and restoration of biodiversity, but such legal levers clearly have limited transformative potential for both biodiversity and justice. The right to a healthy environment, while significant, is strongly influenced by western conceptions of human rights which place humans at the centre, and constructs rights-holders as individual humans (Aguila 2021). The conceptualisation of the right to a healthy environment in the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (African Union 1981) has a more collective, but still anthropocentric approach (Aguila 2021), providing that "all peoples shall have the right to a general satisfactory environment favourable to their development" (African Union 1981, art. 24). The human rights of Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities, including those enshrined under UNDRIP, are critically important given the historical exclusion of these peoples' perspectives from law and policy making at both international (Mickelson 2000, p. 54) and national levels, and, if respected, may allow Indigenous relational philosophies to thrive.

Human Rights and Environmental Due Diligence (HREDD) laws are not specific to biodiversity conservation, but apply to diverse environmental harms, including where those environmental harms impact human rights. These laws are a specific supply chain instrument for reforming corporate practice through the hardening of the process of due diligence as defined in the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (United Nations 2011, principle 17; Martin-Ortega 2014). Due diligence is the process by which businesses prevent, address and remedy impacts on human rights and the environment arising from their own operations and business operations to which they may be linked through their supply chain, including but not exclusively biodiversity. Various jurisdictions in Europe have approved HREDD laws, including the European Union, often imposing obligations on certain companies (e.g. over a certain size) to conduct due diligence in their supply chains (European Coalition for Corporate Justice 2016; BMAS 2021; European Parliament 2024). In complex global value chains, there is a great deal of room to hide poor practices and for companies to respond in partial ways due to the systemic constraints on responsible business (Nelson and Flint 2019). Where companies do not adhere to HREDD processes, civil society and community actors do have the potential to take companies to court (Jehangir 2023), but this can also be costly, time consuming and cumbersome, with little chance of success for claimants (De Schutter 2020, pp. 50–51; Savourey 2020; Lichuma 2021, pp. 527–528; Dehbi and Martin-Ortega 2023, pp. 937–939). Such laws reinforce Cartesian dichotomies and only seek to modify corporate behaviour, imposing standardized rules in reductionist approaches to the environment.

The EU recently adopted a Regulation on Deforestation (EUDR), which specifically focuses on supply chains but takes a wider approach to tackling deforestation compared to existing legislative approaches focused on direct drivers which have had limited impact, e.g. supply-side Voluntary Partnership Agreements (VPAs) (Zeitlin and Overdevest 2021) and demand-side EU Timber Regulation (EUTR) (Sotirov et al. 2017). The Regulation prohibits the import and export of seven forest-risk commodities (FRCs), namely, cattle, cocoa, coffee, palm oil, soy, rubber and wood, and any derived products should their production be linked to deforestation (European Parliament and Council of the European Union 2023, art. 3). It obliges value chain companies to exercise mandatory risk-based due diligence to assess and mitigate risks throughout supply chains. It further develops due diligence obligations on operators and traders, specifies minimum inspection levels, introduces a country benchmarking system, and significantly reduces the role of existing trade instruments such as timber legality licensing (under FLEGT VPAs) and private sustainability certification (European Commission 2021). These changes seek to institutionalize new foreign corporate accountability norms and standards in the global South (Berning and Sotirov 2023). FRCs are predominantly produced in third countries, where the EU does not have jurisdiction to dictate production processes. No effective legally binding global agreement exists that can justify and impose sustainability or legality standards for FRC production in both producing and consuming countries (Cashore and Stone 2014). Studies have shown that expectations for the mutual reinforcement of accountability and legitimacy between the state regulation of timber legality and

private regulation of forest sustainability have so far fallen short (Bartley 2014; Dieguez and Sotirov 2021; Marx and Cuypers 2010) raising doubts over the efficacy of either strategy.

While the global and EU forest policy framework is well researched (e.g. Sotirov et al. 2020; Zeitlin and Overdevest 2021), there are few existing studies on the EU zero-deforestation policy. Mandatory due diligence of FRC supply chains, while a politically feasible policy option to reduce global deforestation (Bager et al. 2021), suffers persistent accountability weaknesses in the EUDR design (e.g. corporate reporting, legal liability, and state monitoring) (Schilling-Vacaflor et al. 2021) with an overly narrow scope (impacts on forests) excluding other critical ecosystems to avoid displacement of agricultural production to grasslands and wetlands. The European Commission may expand the regulation to other natural ecosystems within two years (Halleux 2022). There are potential negative impacts on smallholders, Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPLCs) due to supply chain exclusions (price premiums on included commodities may be inadequate to cover the costs of compliance) and heightened land-use pressures which could result in smallholders and IPLCs being further pushed onto marginal lands (Zhunusova et al. 2022). The EUDR may have quite far-reaching impacts (more research is needed), but there are clearly limitations in its reinforcement of human-nature dichotomies and scope in seeking to reform corporate practice, rather than reshape economies by challenging capitalist relations, potentially advancing of corporate power and obscuring alternatives. The transformative potential of environmental laws and human rights and environmental and deforestation due diligence are summarised in the Table 2.

Rights of nature and legal personhood: exploring the transformative potential of Earth jurisprudence

In response to ongoing socio-ecological damage, there have been calls for the adoption of a new body of law, based on the philosophy of Earth Jurisprudence. In a broad legal philosophy, humans are “only one part of a wider community of beings” and “the welfare of each member of that community is dependent on the welfare of the earth as a whole” (Cullinan 2011, p. 13). This underpins the legal approach to qualify natural entities as possessing legal personality and a subject of rights or right-holders. Stone suggested that trees should have legal standing in 1972 (Darpö 2021), and Berry (1999) introduced the concept of “Earth Law”, whereby “the Earth community has three rights: the right to be, the right to habitat, and the right to fulfil its role in the ever-renewing processes of the Earth community” (Darpö 2021). Some scholars identify the potential of the movement “...to create a world where people live in genuine harmony with nature” (Boyd 2017, p. 232). This would challenge anthropocentrism (Gonzalez 2015) and would prioritize the fundamental rights of all living things (the whole Earth community) to exist and live in a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment (Kauffman and Martin 2017, pp. 131–132). Within Earth jurisprudence, ecosystems granted legal personhood have the right to defend themselves against environmental degradation caused by anthropogenic interference, either through development or climate change (Challe 2021).

Table 2 Assessing the transformative potential of environmental laws and human rights and environmental and deforestation due diligence

Legal lever	Human–nature relations	Capitalist accumulation	Practicality/feasibility	Overall assessment
National and international Biodiversity laws	Moves beyond anthropocentrism, but at times reinforces Cartesian dichotomies, focusing on either biodiversity itself, or framing biodiversity as necessary for human survival. In both cases, implementation of such legal approaches has led to dispossession and violations of rights for Indigenous Peoples	May contribute to some limits on capitalist accumulation, but to a limited degree, simultaneously obscuring the potential for post-growth, pluriversal economic alternatives. Utilization of these laws in reducing global consumption and production patterns has been limited	International laws rely on national compliance with international agreements. Limited scope for sanctions in event of non-compliance. National laws rely on the establishment of effective institutional framework to monitor compliance	Less transformative potential
Human Rights Environmental Due Diligence	As above	May contribute to very small modification in corporate behaviour by requiring businesses to consider the impact of their (and their supply chains) operations on human rights and environment. But limits on capitalist accumulation are few. Obscures alternative economies and does not fundamentally transform economies. (May encourage intrinsic values of nature to be recognized)	Control-oriented, governmentality is key to this approach (e.g. standardized procedures) to fit a uniform world, nature viewed as a resource for management and exploitation	Less transformative potential
Deforestation Due Diligence	Mainly anthropocentric, although makes steps towards addressing damage to nature Nature is seen as a resource to be used, e.g. timber for global value chains, but wisely managed	As above	As above	Less transformative potential

In North America, Pennsylvanian lawyers created the Community Environmental Legal Defense Fund (CELDF) to address environmental harms (Garver 2020), drafting legislation or constitutional provisions recognizing RoN. Elsewhere, Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador, India, New Zealand have adopted various legal mechanisms granting RoN or legal personhood to various nonhuman phenomena (Garver 2020; Darpö 2021). Ecuador was the first country to adopt the RoN doctrine, referred to as the Rights of Pachamama (Mother Earth) (Challe 2021). The constitution acknowledges “an integral respect for nature’s existence and for the maintenance and regeneration of its life cycles, structures, functions, evolutionary processes, and restoration” (Berros 2015). This was groundbreaking for affording positive rights to nature, e.g. specific rights such as rights to restoration and providing legal standing to anyone in Ecuador to protect nature, regardless of their relationship to it (Republic of Ecuador 2008, pp. 10, 71–74). Bolivia has taken similar steps since 2010, hosting the first World People’s Conference on Climate Change and the Rights of Mother Earth, during which the ‘Universal Declaration of the Rights of Mother Earth’ was adopted (GARN 2010). In Colombia (2018) the Supreme Court of Justice ruled in favour of a group of indigenous youth to protect the Amazon from deforestation. The plaintiffs were able to demonstrate how the Colombian government had failed to meet its obligation to reduce deforestation by 2020 as required by the Paris Agreement. The court recognized the Colombian Amazon as a subject of rights; “entitled to protection, conservation, maintenance, and restoration led by the State and territorial agencies.”³ New Zealand’s Whanganui River was granted rights of personhood in 2017 (Tanasescu 2017). It now has legal standing, and two guardians are appointed to represent the rights of the river and its wellbeing—one from an Indigenous community and one from the Crown (Talbot-Jones 2014). The river Turag in Bangladesh was recognized as a ‘living legal entity with rights’ in 2019 (ClientEarth 2019), as was the Los Cedros Forest in Ecuador, generating the revocation of previously granted mining permits and the prohibition of any further extractive activities (GARN 2021; Prieto 2021). At the time of writing (April 2024) a new treaty was formed by Pacific Indigenous leaders from the

Cook Islands, French Polynesia, Aotearoa (New Zealand) and Tonga, recognizing whales and dolphins as legal persons (Doornbos and Whitehead 2024).

RoN are classed as a 'more transformative' legal policy and regulatory solution to biodiversity losses (IPBES 2022), an argument we explore in more detail below. Some case studies begin to provide insights into the potential and challenges of RoN. For Wesche (2021), success depends on the scale of implementation and degree of enforcement, based on his study of the first four years of implementation of the Constitutional Court of Colombia's (2016) orders with respect to the Atrato River arising from its decision in the Centre for Social Justice Studies et al. v Presidency of the Republic et al. Following an analysis of monitoring committee implementation reports, and interviews with experts, Wesche found that the institutional arrangements ordered by the court (i.e. Commission of Guardians of the River) have led to a more coordinated and participatory approach to the formulation of public policies to enforce the Atrato river's rights to protection and maintenance and related community biocultural rights (Wesche 2021, pp. 543–544, 547–548). Local communities have greater policymaking influence, "a major advance in a country, where public policies for far-off and historically neglected regions such as Chocó" are often developed by persons who have never visited and enhanced their environmental awareness (Wesche 2021, p. 548).

However, significant challenges also arose. In terms of enforcing the rights of the river through judicial means, it is unclear whether the Guardianship body and Colombia's Ministry of Environment (MoE) possess such an ability to institute proceedings. Assumptions have been made about the Guardianship body's ability, for example, whether it could become a party in criminal proceedings during which it could file applications and receive compensation. However, these have not been tested in Court (Wesche 2021, p. 550). As for the MoE, Ministry interviewees argue they lack possession of legal personality and argue grievances should be addressed by competent authorities (Wesche 2021, p. 550). Furthermore, communities focused on policy orders reflecting their overall vision for the territory, lifeways and autonomous development, rather than on seeking to enforce the rights of the river against actors in criminal or civil proceedings due to security challenges (Wesche 2021, p. 552). The presence of organised armed and criminal groups conducting illegal mining prevents guardians acting against local public or private actors due to security and physical integrity risks (Wesche 2021, p. 552). In terms of the action plans, whilst State entities invested considerable time into their development, only the eradication of illegal mining plan was adopted in the time limit of the court (Wesche 2021, p. 544). Efforts to strengthen legal and institutional frameworks to tackle illegal mining (improving relations with local communities, better articulation of intelligence activities, criminal investigations) lacked clear targets and baseline indicators against which performance could be measured and lacked community participation (Wesche 2021, pp. 544–545). The MoE engaged community guardians, local communities and relevant state entities. This led to the adoption of an extensive restoration plan that according to community guardians, fully incorporated their views. Other state entities adopted a reactive approach to the ruling, not communicating with the river guardians and communities and essentially submitted plans which constituted inventories of their projects in the region (Wesche 2021, pp. 547–548). Community guardians lack resources to guide the implementation of the restoration plan over twenty years and legal education (Wesche 2021, pp. 549, 551). Thus, once legal recognition has been achieved (which is challenging as most legal systems are inherently anthropocentric), implementation barriers are significant. This impedes efforts to hold violators to account, as accumulation pressures remain high, such that economic development continues to supersede conservation. Transforming an entire economy dependent on illegal mining will be a complex process in contexts of poverty, conflict, weak institutions and corruption (Wesche 2021, p. 551). This raises questions about whether RoN can address capitalist imperatives without broader global actions for example (we discuss this in more detail below). Additionally, ecosystems often cross-cut political jurisdictions, which means that aligning local to global RoN laws and regulations will be necessary to protect ecosystems and address global scale climate and biodiversity challenges. Legal scholars have found that lack of precedent and legal clarity is a challenge (Kurki 2022) which prevent their uptake or lead to inconsistencies in application. Unintended impacts may include displacement of local communities relying upon natural resources. This lack of clarity stems from the clash between anthropocentric and biocentric approaches, which sustain divisions between humans and nature, which become embedded and retained in law.

To assess the transformative potential of RoN, we return to our key questions. While offering a promising framework for protecting and preserving ecosystems—a clear advance on purely anthropocentric approaches—there remain not only practical challenges, but also potential risks of reproducing human–nature dichotomies, which has real-world effects. Gómez-Betancur (2020) questions the RoN doctrine, arguing that a purely conservationist model of rights of nature (which recognizes the intrinsic value of nature free from interference from humans) may preclude humans from accessing the natural environment. This then reproduces an antagonistic relationship between humans and nature and enables the forced removal of indigenous groups to create human-free zones (Büscher and Fletcher 2019). Ignoring the historical relations of local Afro- and Indigenous communities to land, the RoN reinforces these dichotomies (GómezBetancur 2020, p. 76) which are part of colonial modernities (Arora and Stirling 2023). Garver (2020) also reviews RoN and suggests that granting legal personhood to nature is insufficiently radical, due to the focus on ensuring humans care for nature rather than endowing nature with rights: “the overarching goal of the rights of nature movement is to prohibit or constrain human activity that overly harms other elements of the ecosystems in which humans are embedded, or those ecosystems as a whole” (Garver 2020, p. 94). Alternatively, a pluralistic approach entangles humans into nature; drawing on Braverman he states: “Instead of incorporating rights that give nature legal personhood, ecological law should ultimately be about adopting principles and rules that give people naturehood in the law” (Braverman 2018, p. 135 as cited in Garver 2020, pp. 90–91). Naturehood involves “...new understandings of the proper balance between humans and other members of Earth’s life systems (Garver 2020, p. 100). It draws upon Indigenous Peoples and other relational and animist philosophies which respect the spirituality, value and interdependent nature of all life. Indigenous Vedda ontologies (Sri Lanka) and Aboriginal worldviews (Australia) also challenge categorisation, homogenisation and colonisation of ontologies (Edirisinghe and Suchet-Pearson 2024) in the same vein. Without naturehood to humans, RoN may fall short of its transformative potential, except in cases where local communities themselves already have relational philosophies and ethics of care guiding their Guardianship of nature with rights. The granting of naturehood to people is needed, around the world, where such philosophies and values are not widely held and practiced. This means more than legal shifts but ontological ones as well (Edirisinghe and Suchet-Pearson 2024)

Ecocide

Ecocide is not an internationally recognized crime, so individuals or states cannot yet be prosecuted for destroying the Earth (Robinson 2022; Minkova 2023). The international crime of ‘environmental destruction’ exists, applying solely during wartime without broader applicability. The organization ‘Stop Ecocide International’ (SEI n.d.), established in 2017, seeks to add Ecocide to the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court (ICC) to sit alongside other core international crimes: genocide, war crimes and crimes against humanity, to make it an arrestable offence, liable to criminal prosecution (SEI n.d.). Using international criminal law—the only international legal system that focuses on individual criminal responsibility—this would hold individual actors rather than states accountable for their actions and subject them to harsh penalties for crimes (Minkova 2023). “By levying responsibility on persons, not legal fictional entities (i.e. a corporation), the cycle of destruction and accrual of silent rights (the right to pollute, the right to destroy) will die” (Higgins 2012 as cited in Minkova 2023 p. 71). As environmental harms are often committed by wealthy actors situated in the global north (while those who are disproportionality impacted are often located in the global south), the crime of Ecocide can be used to target and prosecute the crimes of the powerful (Robinson 2022).

SEI commissioned an Independent Expert Panel (IEP) for the Legal Definition of Ecocide: “unlawful or wanton acts committed with knowledge that there is a substantial likelihood of severe and either widespread or long-term damage to the environment being caused by those acts” (Stop Ecocide Foundation 2021). Five key terms were defined:

1. ‘Wanton’: with reckless disregard for damage which would be clearly excessive in relation to the social and economic benefits anticipated.
2. ‘Severe’: damage which involves very serious adverse changes, disruption or harm to any element of the environment, including grave impacts on human life or natural, cultural or economic resources.

3. 'Widespread': damage which extends beyond a limited geographic area, crosses state boundaries, or is suffered by an entire ecosystem or species or a large number of human beings.

4. 'Long-term': damage which is irreversible, or which cannot be redressed through natural recovery within a reasonable period of time.

5. 'Environment': the earth, its biosphere, cryosphere, lithosphere, hydrosphere and atmosphere, and outer space (SEI n.d.).

Adding Ecocide to the Rome statute of the ICC would have practical/operational benefits as the ICC provides an enforcement mechanism and symbolically, the Statute underscores the gravity of the crime (Robinson 2022). It would act as a deterrent, reinforcing existing environmental laws and making non-binding multilateral agreements (e.g. the Paris agreement) easier to adhere to and would render the destruction of nature as culturally taboo. However, there are major challenges. The ICC is already failing to manage the crimes it currently has under its remit (Robinson 2022) and the threshold for this crime is unrealistic: it cannot prosecute corporations as the ICC only has jurisdiction over natural persons (Bilotta 2019). In other words, it can only prosecute individuals working within a corporation, not the corporation itself.⁴ Environmental crimes often are transboundary involving diverse decision-makers (Gill 2023) and there is a lack of consensus on criteria, making Ecocide difficult to prosecute (Bilotta 2019; Gill 2023). Finally, the ICC has limited reach; certain countries have not ratified the Rome Statute such as China, Russia and the US (Gill 2023).

Alternatively, a convention could incorporate Ecocide into state domestic laws, as well as a range of lesser environmental crimes broadening the proposition and extending definition beyond intentional action to include negligence (Robinson 2022). Furthermore, states could agree on a declaration of what constitutes the crime of Ecocide, alongside a commitment to add the crime into domestic legislation (Robinson 2022). Nationally, several countries have or are seeking to make Ecocide a crime (Kaminski 2023). Belgium was the first European country to recognize Ecocide under international law. The crime applies to "individuals in the highest positions of decision-making power and to corporations" (Cottam 2024). Punishment for the crime could include a 20-year prison sentence or a €1.6 million fine. In July 2023 Mexico submitted a bill to its parliament to criminalize Ecocide, drawing on the IEP definition (Kaminski 2023). Brazil has proposed an Ecocide bill. Other states have criminalized Ecocide including Vietnam, Ukraine and Russia (Kaminski 2023), while several European countries have submitted draft laws. Enforcement issues are significant. In Guatemala, despite legally recognizing Ecocide and finding a palm oil corporation guilty of damaging waterways and associated eco-systems, the corporation has resumed polluting the river despite the initial ruling. This case supports arguments for the establishment of an internationally recognized crime of Ecocide (Muir 2023) where, as outlined above, the ICC would provide an enforcement mechanism.

Legislative processes aside, further shortcomings remain. Firstly, despite the potential of Ecocide to challenge capitalist relations, the inclusion of the "wantonness element" reinforces existing dichotomies between humans and nature. The wantonness criteria included in the definition—which concerns itself only with actions considered in excess to social and economic benefits resulting from certain actions—will exclude actions that do not meet this threshold (Minkova 2023, p. 74). The current definition of Ecocide "allows those instances of environmental damage that do not "clearly" exceed the benefits to society to escape the reach of the law" (Minkova 2023, p. 74). In other words, the cost to the environment is deemed secondary to the benefits of humans.

At present, the IEP measures the wantonness criteria against the concept of sustainable development which it believes will provide a solid foundation for ensuring a proper balance between nature and society (Minkova 2023; Branch and Minkova 2023). This is problematic, as in reality, sustainable development envisions continued growth and does not tackle accumulation imperatives. Furthermore, using dam construction as one example, Minkova demonstrates how "the IEP's definition creates the misleading perception that abstract concepts such as 'environmental costs' and 'socio-economic benefits' can be separated and determined in practice" (Minkova 2024, p. 82). In this instance, while some actors may benefit from better access to water or hydroelectric power, this does not negate the environmental damage caused by the construction

of the dam, nor the potentially extensive impact on displaced communities. This raises the question; 'Who and what interests and values are taken into account? We will return to this shortly.

Interestingly the IEP offers little in terms of clarifying which socio-economic benefits it is referring to. It briefly mentions that these could include "housing developments and transport links", but it does not outline how the social or economic benefits of these examples outweigh the environmental damage they would cause (see Minkova 2024). Furthermore, terms such as these suggest one-off events (Minkova 2024). Robinson (2022) reminds us that our everyday activities, such as travel, work, and consumption, all contribute to ecological harms. Hence, cost-benefit analysis would need to cover both one-off events linked to public, private and third sectors and daily practices. Doing so could be paralysing and imply more far-reaching degrowth solutions, which are proving hard to build public and political support for. The lack of support should not rule out consideration of such an approach, but they would be ambitious and would require a means of implementation.

Some suggest that green growth ecomodernist approaches could fit with a sustainable development approach that can deliver on the needs of current society without compromising the needs of future generations to avoid such trade-offs (Branch and Minkova 2023). However, evidence that green growth is being achieved on the timescale, duration and magnitude required is lacking. Another approach would be to engage in a process of 'compartmentaliz[ing]' socio-ecological harms (Boukli and Kotsakis) by dividing harms into separate components and applying different legal instruments to address each one (as cited by Minkova 2024). Creating flexibility in judgements is another alternative. Minkova (2024) recommends the ICC embrace principles of reflexivity and normativity to recognize the interconnectedness between social and environmental harms. This would allow for more flexibility in cases of ecocide where moral judgements could replace objective legal practice and where terms such as ecological degradation would not be restricted to scientific meanings. This approach would encourage value judgements on expert knowledge, and judges would be expected to ask questions such as: Who has the authority to represent such expert knowledge and whose voices have been silenced? Allied to this is the question of how impact is measured and whose interests, values and voice matter more. Here Minkova offers two options: the egalitarian approach (ascribing equal value to the benefits of all) or the prioritarian approach (ascribing more value to the benefits of the worst-off). This discourse completely ignores non-human agency and casts Nature as a passive, external entity, rather than as something that could be represented in such moral judgements—something which could, obviously, be changed with public pressure and by social movements.

Ultimately, it is our contention that the wantonness criterion undermines the central tenet of this crime: to punish those who commit environmental crimes that result in the destruction of the earth. As Heller (2021) argues: it "has no place in the definition of Ecocide...How the IEP can justify calling such an anthropocentric understanding of environmental destruction 'Ecocide' is difficult to understand." Instead, "Ecocide" should be defined as "acts committed with awareness that there is a substantial likelihood of severe and either widespread or long-term damage to the environment being caused by those acts, where a reasonable person would know that the expected environmental damage would be clearly excessive in relation to the social and economic benefits anticipated" (Heller 2021). On this basis, a moral judgement is made on the severity and temporality of the harms being caused.

The authors concede, that from a purely legal standpoint, the wantonness criteria, as outlined in the draft article to amend the Rome Statute, does recognise criminal recklessness. For some, the current definition, despite the caveats outlined above, can be a good solution, especially when considering other alternatives.⁵ Nevertheless, we maintain the importance of highlighting the inherent anthropocentrism underpinning the definition. Ideally, by removing the wantonness element, such a definition (and naming of the crime) would enable the concept of Ecocide to better capture the entanglement of human–nature relations

As noted above, Ecocide has the potential to challenge capitalist relations; however, we envisage barriers in this regard. In stark terms, capitalism is leading to 'ecologically induced genocide' (Crook and Short 2014, p. 299), because of the accumulation and extraction of products and resources which is destroying environments and human populations being dispossessed and expelled from the land. Scholars refer to this as the genocide–Ecocide nexus (Crook and Short 2014; Crook et al.

2018). They posit that the ‘invasion’ and ‘annexation’ of indigenous land—resulting in cultural and social destruction of Indigenous Peoples forcibly removed from their land—meets the criteria contained within definition of genocide (Crook and Short 2014; Crook et al. 2018). “[F]or those Indigenous Peoples fighting to retain or regain their lands, they are fighting for their life as distinct peoples since, for them, their spirituality and cultural vitality is based in and on and with their lands. If we take this point seriously when this relationship is forcibly interrupted and breaks down due to expansionist land grabs driven by global capitalism, the genocide lens becomes appropriate” (Crook and Short 2014, p. 313).

In terms of transformative potential, Ecocide is clearly driven by colonial modernities, which cast nature and certain peoples as being of lesser value and available for control and exploitation (of which capitalism is one manifestation, another example being state socialism). Ecocide could present a transformative option if the definition is clarified to more fully address capitalist pressures and colonial modernities. It also needs to remove the wantonness element to overcome the rigidity of human–nature dichotomies, recognizing that it is not only in Indigenous Peoples’ contexts where human–nature entanglements are central to sustainability futures. In some ways, the concept of Ecocide has a bio- or ecocentric framing and might better be conceptualised as *socionaturecide*, to recognize the existential threats of harms to the flourishing of all life on Earth.

Environmental courts and tribunals

Given some of the implementation challenges of RoN and Ecocide, we explore here their application in court processes. Several international agreements and policing initiatives address international environmental crimes (Walters and Westerhuis 2013),⁶ e.g. environmental courts and tribunals (ECTs), which have existed since the 1970s. There are 2,115 operational ECTs in 67 countries (UN Environment Programme 2016), ranging from fully formed independent judicial branch bodies, made up of trained expert staff with large budgets to small, underfunded village courts, with rotating judges that deal with environmental cases once a month (UNEP 2016). Environmental tribunals can be either complex administrative-branch bodies or local community land use planning boards (see UNEP 2016). There are challenges associated with ECTs, e.g. risks of sidelining environmental cases, plus issues relating to the definition of what is considered an environmental issue. Overall, however, ECTs could provide a pathway for implementing RoN. The expertise, efficiency, visibility and lower costs of ECTs are positives, offering greater accountability for crimes against nature, visible government support and a focus for public attention (UNEP 2021). They increase opportunities to use alternative dispute resolutions, such as Restorative Justice, which enable prosecutions, but promote non-adversarial dispute resolving processes.

Restorative justice

Restorative Justice is a form of justice that considers the needs of the victim, offender, and the wider community, giving voice to victims through active listening, bringing together the victim, offender, and others impacted by the crime, to reach a resolution. Emphasis is placed on “harm reparation, social restoration, community harmony, and problem-solving” (White 2014, p. 43). Restorative Justice gives victims “opportunity to express their needs and to participate in determining the best way for the offender to make reparation...” (Preston 2011, p. 3). This is more difficult when the victim is a nonhuman entity. Used in environmental crime cases, active listening extends beyond the human world to hear the voice of nature and ascertain differing significance that people attach to different nonhuman entities (White 2014). To tackle the politics of representation within multi-species justice, initiatives are underway to allow nonhumans to speak with ‘an active voice’, e.g. via arts-based methods.

Restorative Justice has been used in cases of small-scale environmental offences by local companies in Australia, New Zealand, and Canada. In the latter two, trees and rivers have been acknowledged as victims of environmental crime and represented by Indigenous organizations (Wijdekop 2019). In their review of case law from these countries, the International Union for Conservation of Nature identified the following outcomes in these cases: apologies, restoration of the harm done to the environment, including prevention of future harms, monetary compensation to victims and community service work (Wijdekop 2019).

Using Restorative Justice in cases of environmental crime can (i) empower victims by giving them a voice, (ii) require the offender to take responsibility and listen to the harm they have caused, and

(iii) offers the community an opportunity to take control of the case, allowing them to have an active role in reaching a resolution (Preston 2011). Giving nature a voice has the potential to transform humanity's relationship with environments other than humans (Preston 2011). Preston (2011) identifies the following victims of environmental crime: specific individuals, classes of persons, members of a community, future generations, and environment other than humans. Members of a community are inextricably linked to the environment in which the community exists. Therefore, when the environment is harmed or damaged so too is the community (Preston 2011, p. 11). Humans are not and will not be the only victims of environmental crime. "The biosphere and non-human biota have intrinsic value independent of their utilitarian or instrumental value for humans. When harmed by environmental crime, the biosphere and non-human biota also are victims (Preston 2011).⁸ While we concur with the sentiment that both humans and nature are affected by environmental crimes, we note that Preston's argument reinforces human–nature dichotomies. He argues for privilege to 'the Indigenous voice' because of their intrinsic identification with the land (White 2014), but care is needed to avoid essentializing Indigenous Peoples and instead focus on their ontologies which can vary and are changing. In some instances, they may include relationality and ethics of care values; however, in many other contexts globally, such philosophies and values are sidelined. Below we review two cases to assess the transformative potential of using Restorative Justice in environmental courts.

Garrett v Williams 2007

Restorative Justice was used in a case involving environmental crime—Garrett v Williams in 2007. In this case, a mining company, without consent, excavated Aboriginal lands, causing harm to Aboriginal objects thereby contravening the National Parks and Wildlife Act 1974. Williams, the guilty party, pleaded guilty to the offence against s 90(1) of the National Parks and Wildlife Act 1974 (NPW Act) (NSW 1974). The act states that: "A person who, without first obtaining the consent of the Director-General, knowingly destroys, defaces or damages, or knowingly causes or permits the destruction or defacement of or damage to, an Aboriginal object or Aboriginal place is guilty of an offence against this Act. Maximum penalty: 50 penalty units or imprisonment for 6 months, or both (or 200 Penalty units in the case of a corporation" (Hamilton 2008). Before sentencing, the Judge set up a Restorative Justice conference between Williams, the local Wilyakali people and prosecutors (McDonald 2008; Walters and Westerhuis 2013). Harm was deemed to have been done to both 'place' and those identifying with the 'place', i.e. harm was done to both humans and nonhumans. The Court only explicitly addressed the impact on humans (White 2014). Recognizing the nature–human relations imbued in many Indigenous cosmologies, "the specific material and cultural positioning of Indigenous people within certain landscapes is vital to understanding the nature of environmental victimisation in cases such as Williams" (White 2014, p. 47). In the words of Dodson: "Everything about Aboriginal society is inextricably interwoven with, and connected to, the land. Culture is the land, the land and spirituality of Aboriginal people, our cultural beliefs or reason for existence is the land. You take that away and you take away our reason for existence. We have grown the land up. We are dancing, singing and painting for the land. We are celebrating the land. Removed from our lands, we are literally removed from ourselves" (Dodson 1997 as cited in White 2014, p. 48). This shows the importance of challenging "'white' understandings of nature and the nature–human relationship" (White 2014) and privileging the knowledge and lived experience of Indigenous Peoples. This, White (2014) argues, is what occurred in Garrett v Williams 2007. The New South Wales Land and Environment Court went to great efforts to ensure that the Indigenous voice was given primacy over and above other types of so-called expert evidence (White 2014, p. 50).

Restorative Justice in this case embraced a different philosophy to the dominant colonial modernity and hence represents a way of overcoming Cartesian dichotomies and challenging capitalist relations. "Restorative remedies... promise to tackle environmental damage not per se, but vis-à-vis the broader harm to relation. Thus, restorative solutions are better suited than traditional punishments to rebalance the anthropocentric and eco-centric components embedded in environmental harm" (Porfido 2021, p. 114).

Given its recognition that human–nature relations are entangled, (often) spiritual and sacred, Restorative Justice has the potential to support transformative change for multispecies justice, when combined with RoN. However, we suggest that this is only the case where local communities have relational philosophies and ethics of care or are supported to unlearn them. Contemporary imaginaries of human–nature relations are constrained, with material effects, suppressing more

pluriversal MTH imaginaries and formations. In some contexts, local communities have very instrumental imaginaries of rivers, for example, and Nature as a whole, but not in all: continuity is assumed between the Whanganui River in New Zealand and Maori peoples for example. In Bangladesh, more limited rights are granted to rivers; rather than being treated as persons, rivers are in the stated custody of human persons, who should protect them for the public good, not for the intrinsic values of nature, and certainly no naturehood is ascribed to humans, aligning with normative Muslim perspectives (Khan n.d.). In Bangladesh, there has not been facilitation of Indigenous perspectives to inform RoN discourse and reimagine rivers both in legal jurisprudence/instruments and more broadly (Khan n.d.). In many modern societies, imbued with invisible colonial modernities (Arora and Stirling 2023) processes of unlearning and undoing colonial modernities and co-creating new river–human and more broadly nature–human relation imaginaries and formations will be ever more essential for pluriversal sustainability transformations. Restorative Justice could be combined with emancipatory education processes, as well as support for social movements.

More specifically, within legal contexts, mock trials can advance awareness of new propositions. In 2011 a Mock Ecocide Trial was held in the Supreme Court of England and Wales to demonstrate the viability of introducing this crime. Two fictional Chief Executive Officers (CEO) were put on trial for causing Ecocide. The cases in question were the Deepwater Horizon Oil Disaster in the Gulf of Mexico and Unconventional oil extraction in Alberta, Canada (Wijdekop 2019). Both CEOs were found guilty of Ecocide. Following their convictions, a Restorative Justice hearing was established (The Hamilton Group 2011). Only one of the CEOs took part. He was joined by various spokespersons: one for the birds impacted by the environmental crimes, one for future generations, one for the wider community, one for the Earth and a representative from the Indigenous People affected by the crimes. The mock trial was considered successful in enabling dialogue between diverse human and non-human entities, all aimed at giving voice, healing and restoration, generating pathways for mending damage (Wijdekop 2019).

4.5 Discussion

A combination is needed of RoN (especially embracing naturehood to persons), Ecocide, Restorative Justice and environmental courts, plus emancipatory education, social movements and socio-cultural engagements, and arts with communities who are steeped in solely instrumentalist relations to enable recovery and creation of new MTH ontologies and praxis. This is relevant especially in specific geographies where colonial modernities are intense.

Multi-species justice, from an ontological viewpoint, treats all beings as equal. This aligns with African and indigenous notions of collective rights which seek to replace individualized notions of human rights (see IPBES 2022). The former refers to the rights of all living beings: “trees, forests, other plant and animal species, water bodies, and a variety of other physical and metaphysical entities, whether visible or otherwise, such as sacred landscapes” (Crawhall 2023). While such expansive understandings of rights challenge Cartesian dichotomies and colonial modernities (Quijano 2000; Arora and Stirling 2023)—which have enabled the appropriation of nature—they still work with the concept of ‘rights’, rather than ancestral claims to territory. The imposition of proprietary rights on non-proprietary lands with ancestral claims, while giving scope to create Indigenous rights, created potential for their alienation, which continues to this day (German 2022). Onto-epistemologically, pluriversality and justice are thus challenging to combine given that Western notions of justice are inherently limiting, but multi-species justice thinking can at least promote deeper changes in legal systems and socio-cultural norms, focusing attention on empathy and care between humans and more-than-human-worlds. See Table 3 for a summary of the transformative potential of Rights of Nature, Ecocide, environmental course and Restorative Justice.

Tackling capitalism and colonial modernities

Specific measures and struggles are needed to dismantle capitalist relations and the broader colonial modernity formation of which they are an example. We cannot cover these in depth, but legal examples that could contribute to challenges to capitalist relations might include the following: legal levers to control corporate power and re-shape financial systems (e.g. anti-monopoly regulation, prevention of mergers and acquisitions that create excessive market concentration, expansion of public banking); laws to redistribute wealth and power (including progressive taxation, given that environmental impacts are disproportionately higher among high-

net-worth individuals see Oxfam International 2023); stricter rules on corporate political lobbying to prevent the thinning of democracy (Standing 2016); legal measures to redistribute land from private control to enable community land ownership and enterprise; deliberative democracy (e.g. citizen assemblies and participatory budgeting). This includes political will, public acceptance, international coordination and economic stability (Kallis et al. 2012). Some of these critical eco-Marxism propositions are strong on challenging capitalist relations, but do not yet address anthropocentrism (e.g. labour laws currently focus solely on human workers, neglecting the labour of non-human species) nor colonial modernities. They leave political logics intact and so are not trans-hegemonic in nature in terms of sustainability transformations (Hamilton and RamcilovicSuominen 2023). Shifts in onto-epistemologies and values created by social movements and converging coalitions are needed to facilitate pluriversal, trans-hegemonic approaches that address and escape colonial modernities. This means support for ontological recovery and creativity, through struggle, arts, and critical pedagogy, to curate shifts in consciousness and ways of being relating to the agency and vitality of non-humans as part of more-than-human assemblages—underpinned by ethics of care for flourishing earthly life (Nelson et al. forthcoming).

4.6 Conclusion

Seeking to establish whether the law has a role in the achievement of pluriversal, multi-species justice sustainability transformations, we have explored the ability of legal pathways and levers to challenge rigid Cartesian dichotomies and other related dimensions of colonial modernities, including capitalist accumulation. We find that existing environmental laws and supply chain legal measures have significant limitations in this regard. Such laws continue to reinforce anthropocentrism and fail to transform (hence likely reproducing) capitalist relations, while potentially having some localized benefits, but leaving political logics and ontologies unchallenged. Earth jurisprudence and RoN are a significant step forward. These will have most efficacy when Indigenous and relational philosophies are embraced more broadly in society and in their design, e.g. granting naturehood to persons in mainstream ontology and amplifying relational philosophies in communities or co-creating these where absent. These advances can be put into practice in contexts where environmental courts and Restorative Justice can be applied. Solely biocentric approaches risk the reinforcement of human–nature dichotomies. We recognize that more far-reaching changes are needed in justice systems and beyond in colonial modernity formations to recognize Indigenous and relational philosophies and allow space for speculations and prefiguring of alternative futures. Challenges of violence and insecurity stem from accumulation imperatives and colonial modernities and hence need to be countered by measures that tackle them, such as Ecocide deterrents and dismantling measures, while in the shorter term investing in peace building. Inclusion in the ICC is a long-term project for Ecocide. In the more immediate future, combining RoN, Ecocide and Restorative Justice can provide a practical way to re-balance concerns for human needs and ecological ones. This will give voice to communities that prioritize reciprocity and care as a step on the way towards opening more radical pluriversal futures, which involve ontological regeneration and changes. Achieving transformative change will require struggle and political coalitions, well-designed governmental levers and possibly eco-anarchist approaches and speculative art engagements which escape the entanglements of the nation state in capitalism and colonial modernities. Reframing the law and justice systems to embrace MTH philosophies and multispecies justice is needed, where this is linked to critical pedagogy and decolonial and relational artistic, academic and transdisciplinary action-research to challenge and shift public ontologies. The latter can help to escape from colonial modernities by creating new future sustainability possibilities. This can represent a step—for it is only a step—on a path towards more foundational shifts away from dominating and controlling colonial modernities to care-and solidarity-based ethics and formations.

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Declarations

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Table 1: A conceptual framework for reflexivity on potential levers for sustainability transformations (Nelson et al, submitted)

Assessing levers or initiatives for sustainability	Status quo	Less transformative potential (blocking)	More transformative potential
To what extent does it overcome rigid Cartesian dichotomies and create space for care-oriented imaginaries recognizing entanglements, non-human agency & nature as kin (Onto-epistemological shifts).	Anthropocentric Prioritises human-oriented perspectives with a rigid dichotomy between humans and nature. Does not recognize nature as kin.	Biocentric Prioritizes bio- or eco-centric perspectives, retaining the rigid dichotomy between humans and nature. Does not generally recognize nature as kin, i.e. having agency and labour.	Pluriversal Recognizes interdependencies and entanglements between humans and nature, possibly including nature as kin, i.e. having agency and labour. Amplifies relational ontologies.
To what extent do they directly or indirectly challenge accumulation and promote autonomous regeneration via pluriversal post-growth?	Status quo capitalist No constraints on consumption, no shifts in economic visions and structures.	Reformist approach Seeks to modify or reform corporate practice to increase sustainability, treats market economy and growth as common sense, risks obscuring alternatives and does not tackle wider macro-economy and consumption governance.	Convivial, diverse economies Promotes reciprocity focused, post-growth economies, tackles accumulation imperative and growth orientation. with a multi-species justice goal.

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Table 2: Assessing the transformative potential of environmental laws and human rights and environmental and deforestation due diligence

Legal lever	Human-Nature Relations	Capitalist accumulation	Practicality / feasibility	Overall assessment
National and international Biodiversity laws	Moves beyond anthropocentrism, but at times reinforces Cartesian dichotomies, focusing on either biodiversity itself, or framing biodiversity as necessary for human survival. In both cases, implementation of such legal approaches has led to dispossession and violations of rights for Indigenous Peoples.	May contribute to some limits on capitalist accumulation, but to a limited degree, simultaneously obscuring the potential for post-growth, pluriversal economic alternatives. Utilization of these laws in reducing global consumption and production patterns has been limited.	International laws rely on national compliance with international agreements. Limited scope for sanctions in event of non-compliance. National laws rely on the establishment of effective institutional framework to monitor compliance.	Less transformative potential.
Human Rights Environmental Due Diligence	As above	May contribute to very small modification in corporate behaviour by requiring businesses to consider the impact of their (and their supply chains) operations on human rights and environment. But limits on capitalist accumulation are few. Obscures alternative economies and does not fundamentally transform economies. (May encourage intrinsic values of nature to be recognized).	Control-oriented, governmentality is key to this approach (e.g. standardized procedures) to fit a uniform world, nature viewed as a resource for management and exploitation.	Less transformative potential.
Deforestation Due Diligence	Mainly anthropocentric, although makes steps towards addressing damage to nature. Nature is seen as a resource to be used, e.g. timber for global value chains, but wisely managed.	As above.	As above.	Less transformative potential.

Table 3: Analysis of the transformative potential of Rights of Nature, Ecocide, environmental courts and Restorative Justice

Lever	Human-Nature Relations	Capitalist accumulation	Practicality / feasibility	Overall assessment
RoN -Legal personhood	Moves beyond anthropocentrism by ensuring humans respect and care for nature by observing its rights, but it retains distinctions between humans and nature in a more biocentric approach (dichotomies are to a certain extent, upheld).	May challenge capitalist relations with recognition that nature needs to be protected and by giving local communities more power to defend ecosystems.	Economic interests often overshadow environmental concerns. Enforcement challenges exist, especially in contexts of threat of violence. Lack of legal precedent. Cultural, economic, ideological challenges.	Less transformative potential.
RoN - naturehood for people	Challenges rigid human-nature dichotomies, making space for plural philosophies which recognize human-nature entanglement and non-human agency and value (care ethics) by giving people naturehood in law.	May challenge capitalist relations with greater recognition of human-nature interdependencies and impacts of capitalism on these highlighting a greater need for protection. Gives local communities more power to defend socionatures.	As above.	More transformative potential when supported by relational, community philosophies and Restorative Justice.
Ecocide ICC	The wantonness element gives primacy to human benefits (anthropocentric) while also retaining / reinforcing distinctions between humans and nature (biocentric perspectives are also, to a certain extent, upheld).	The IEP definition would allow for prosecuting wealthy actors guilty of committing Ecocide crimes. The cost benefit analysis of the damage done to the earth versus the economic gain, favours the latter. Ecocide tackles the consequences of capitalist accumulation (destruction to the earth) rather than the driving force: capitalism. It can act as a deterrent.	The ICC would provide an enforcement mechanism. Prosecuting individuals is more realistic than prosecuting states. Despite the international focus of the ICC, it still does not have global reach.	Less transformative potential, unless it addresses the inextricable link between capitalism, Ecocide and genocide.
Ecocide as convention	Potential to move beyond anthropocentrism and biocentrism, if the wantonness element contained within the IEP definition is removed and a convention is drafted as outlined by Robinson (2022) and the crimes listed are	If the wantonness element is removed from the definition of Ecocide, then there is the potential to challenge capitalist relations. Has more potential to tackle the root cause of Ecocide, if specific laws are in	State-level implementation may be more feasible as outlined above. It does not address Ecocide committed by the state. Enforcement issues, especially in contexts of insecurity and violence.	More transformative potential but only if the wantonness element is not part of local/state

D2.2 Transformative change pathways on trade, legal actions, and corporate governance report

Lever	Human-Nature Relations	Capitalist accumulation	Practicality / feasibility	Overall assessment
	informed by the RoN naturehood for people doctrine.	place that target extraction, annexation and invasion of indigenous lands.		definitions of Ecocide.
RoN, Restorative Justice and the environmental courts	This combination moves beyond anthropocentrism, where it supports the idea of an Earth community, where all members (human and nonhuman) are valued and protected from harm.	Potential to challenge capitalist relations, by collapsing rigid dichotomies, promoting ethics of care. Gives greater voice to Indigenous Peoples and local communities and their expertise. Can punish those who commit crimes against the earth creating a deterrent effect, but it does not dismantle the capitalist system.	Environmental courts already exist. They vary operationally and there is a lack of a uniform definition on environmental crime. Courts cannot address transnational environmental crimes or crimes committed by transnational corporations. Requires communities with relational philosophies (which highlight the need for emancipatory processes to unlearn colonial modernities and co-create new imaginaries of human-nature relations).	More transformative potential

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